

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D6.1

Stakeholder engagement guidelines,
including toolkit

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Executive Summary

How to bring the wide variety of stakeholders¹ into the increasing complexity of blue economy developments in the most sustainable way, tackling pollution, increasing biodiversity, reducing the carbon footprint and speeding-up the circular processes present in the offshore business and other innovative activities at sea, remains a challenge. The importance of involving stakeholders for addressing such challenges here is clear and includes, but is not limited to:

- helping significantly in raising awareness,
- achieving project targets and objectives,
- managing and assessing risks,
- sharing best practices,
- reducing conflicts whilst applying a transparent principle,
- having a better access to resources
- and information and identifying the gaps more correctly.

This deliverable analyses how to best identify, map and approach stakeholders oriented towards the objectives set in the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”. This approach is designed to help better reaching a sustainable blue economy and the targets and objectives set in line with the Mission. These guidelines are generally applicable towards all four lighthouses: the Atlantic and Arctic Ocean, the Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic and North Sea and the Danube River and Black Sea. Therefore, the team put the objectives of the Mission in line with the most relevant businesses and stakeholders today. The stakeholders approach originates from the Penta-Helix model, at times slightly extending. The team derived a non-exhaustive stakeholder mapping, which provides several examples per country.

From that basis, our team of experts derived a ‘stakeholder interests and needs analysis’, with cases and relevant actions that are topic and stakeholder dependent and that show how one can identify gaps and what is important working on for the application process of new projects but also towards actions in the field. This process took into account the results of the baseline studies conducted for the lighthouses (Baseline study for the implementation of lighthouses of the Mission ‘Restore our ocean and waters by 2030’ Atlantic, Arctic, Danube and Mediterranean lighthouses, Baltic and North Sea lighthouses (Directoraat-generaal Onderzoek en Innovatie (Europese Commissie) 2023)².

Moreover, today’s request to involve all kinds of stakeholders in different kinds of projects to impact the successes, reveals a gap in an overarching or governmental approach to involve stakeholders,

¹ These guidelines work with “stakeholders”, which in our context do not only mean “citizens”. In general, when used in these guidelines and referring to the Toolbox created in WP3 Prep4Blue, (Bjørkan et al. (2023) Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters: A toolbox of approaches. Milestone 6. Prep4Blue.), “citizen” emphasises the non-specialist, non-elite nature of an individual. This creates some distinction from the sometimes-overlapping term stakeholder. Stakeholders, by contrast, may be either specialist, elite, have access to Mission Ocean activities due to their employment, or some other form of contextual privilege. They also tend to be represented as organisations or interest groups, while citizens tend to be engaged as individuals. That said, the two concepts often overlap and, of course, individual stakeholders can also be citizens, and citizens may be stakeholders.

² [Baseline study for the implementation of lighthouses of the Mission ‘Restore our ocean and waters by 2030’ - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#), [Baseline study for the implementation of the lighthouse in the Baltic and North Sea basins for the Mission ‘Restore our ocean and waters by 2030’ - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#).

which includes an assessment of the rights and duties of a stakeholder. It seems that we currently lack precise criteria to determine the legitimacy of an interest's inclusion within the stakeholder group. These guidelines formulate potential ways and frameworks to accommodate for this identified gap.

This work is significantly based on the insights gained during the workshop held in Brussels (Belgium) on 17 October 2023 titled: “stakeHolders2cO-design! Towards impactful stakeholder engagement in the Mission Ocean, Seas and Waters”.

Moreover, some general recommendations, valid for all kind of methods are described. How can one keep the project or action sustainable, and the related community of all kinds of stakeholders, alive? How are good relationships built? How is a project to be monitored and assessed, in terms of relevant stakeholder engagement? How can one integrate gender and other inclusivity criteria and what are the actual rights of a stakeholder? Is this a concept that should be further investigated, and should a changing society adapt its legal framework for stakeholder engagement to promote equal chances and responsibilities?

What for example about a multi-use concept for marine spatial planning within a sustainable blue economy dealing with scarcity of place, that can overarch several previously identified problems (data, monitoring, emission, circularity, ocean pollution and many more), and set big steps towards a sustainable blue economy and the other objectives of the Mission?

Besides, several recommendations are given on how to ideally set a collaborative governance, with several examples of existing institutions and best practice case studies/projects in Europe. Ideally, governmental institutions should be better merged and interlinked, and (inter)-communicate. It must be stressed that together with actions or projects, (limited) budgets apply. Stakeholder engagement is therefore always context dependent. It is therefore recommended to finetune for your action or project the most relevant actors with the most significant and legitimate influences, as well as the most efficient management and budget division. These guidelines provide guidance to balance these aspects.

Finally, the team developed a database showcasing several relevant projects that have been or are active within the Mission and where stakeholder engagement activities have been identified and assessed. The criteria used to select the projects and methodologies serve for future project managers and society to best select methods for stakeholder engagement, and thus successes of the project, as well as an interest for stakeholders that are directly involved as partners in projects supported or even funded by the Mission or actions that were submitted to the Mission charter and stakeholders that are engaged or to be engaged by such projects or actions.

The Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (SHES) as developed in D6.2 seeks to empower stakeholders through deliberative democracy, social innovation, and citizen science, activating their role in driving transitions and ensuring that no community is left behind. In this report, we include a summary of the strategy for Stakeholder involvement (cf. Annex 10.2, M6.1). At its core, the SHES commits to environmental sustainability, economic prosperity, and community involvement, creating a cohesive society benefiting optimally from ecosystem services, energy, and food supply.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
(the) Mission	Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”
EBM	Ecosystem-Based Management
MSP	Marine Spatial Planning
ICZM	Integrated Coastal Zone Management
AT	Austria
BA	Bosnia and Herzegovina
BG	Bulgaria
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
CZ	Czech Republic
DE	Germany
ES	Spain
EUSDR	EU Strategy for the Danube Region
FO/DK	Faroer Islands
FR	France
GL/DK	Greenland
GR	Greece
HR	Croatia
HU	Hungary
IE	Ireland
IS	Iceland
LH(s)	Lighthouse(s)
MD	Republic of Moldova
ME	Montenegro
MO	Mission Ocean and Waters
MPA(s)	Marine Protected Area(s)
NGO(s)	Non-Governmental Organization
NO	Norway
P4B	PREP4BLUE
PT	Portugal
RO	Romania
RS	Serbia
SH(s)	Stakeholder(s)
SHEM	Stakeholder Engagement Methods

SHenG	Stakeholder(s) engagement
SK	Slovakia
SL	Slovenia
UA	Ukraine
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

1 Introduction

Missions are a new instrument in the Horizon Europe program, which aims to tackle large societal challenges with systemic solutions. The implementation of five mission themes (Restore our ocean and waters by 2030, Adaptation to Climate Change, Cancer, Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and Soil Health and Food) was launched in 2021.

Funded under the EU Horizon Europe program, Prep4Blue is a three-year project that sets the scene for co-creating and co-implementing the research and innovation required to achieve the objectives of the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” (hereafter “MO” or (the) Mission) by using the dedicated enablers “Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System” and “Public mobilisation and engagement”.

Within Prep4Blue, WP6 (“Stakeholder Engagement: Strategy, Connectivity and Capacity Building”) as such aims to develop a multidisciplinary, multistakeholder approach including industry and businesses, public authorities, citizens, academia and the Research & Development sector and Civil Society Organisations (CSO’s) to mobilise all sectors and connect with the ocean. In this regard, a PentaHelix approach that adds the natural environment in the process of knowledge production, and the creation of a new innovation is preferred, extensions are added. It is to be noted that these guidelines work with “stakeholders”, which in our context do not only mean “citizens”. In general, when used in this guidelines “citizen” emphasises the non-specialist, non-elite nature of an individual. This creates some distinction from the sometimes-overlapping term stakeholder. Stakeholders, by contrast, may be either specialist, elite, have access to Mission Ocean activities due to their employment, or some other form of contextual privilege. They also tend to be represented as organisations or interest groups, while citizens tend to be engaged as individuals. That said, the two concepts often overlap and, of course, individual stakeholders can also be citizens, and citizens may be stakeholders¹³.

A culture of collaboration and recognition of the environment is fundamental in contributing to social innovation. Ceasing the emotional disconnection of people and ocean by participatory processes is key for succeeding. Therefore, measures and models for impactful stakeholder engagement to co-develop and co-implement the scale-up of innovative solutions for the targets set by the Mission Oceans, seas and Waters are built. This implies capacity building to support stakeholder engagement as well as provide tested and validated methodologies for running stakeholders’ assemblies for the Mission implementation through the piloting of four collaborative processes, one per LH based area. This is implemented following pre-defined criteria, risk & opportunity assessment, cost & value assessment resulting on prioritisation of stakeholders per criterium.

In this deliverable we present guidelines on helping orienting society towards achieving the targets set for the objectives of the mission. Best practices are selected that help projects effectively be designed and methodologies screened and assessed on their relevance for the Mission . This is done per objectives and following dedicated criteria, in line with the most relevant businesses and organisations. This is done to improve protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, to stimulate preventing and eliminating pollution of our ocean, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil and in order to make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy.

Considering the long-term sustainability of ocean-related projects, freshwater ecosystem restoration and offshore initiatives it is good to plan for the future, taking into account changing needs and environmental considerations. Additionally, successful engagement of stakeholders is an ongoing and dynamic process. It requires adaptability and a commitment to building trust and willingness to reach consensus among diverse groups with varying interests and priorities. Collaborative and adaptive governance, described in Chapter 6, is therefore an important factor. Overall, it is important to maintain high levels of transparency and accountability in stakeholder engagement. Ensure that commitments are upheld and that stakeholders' voices are heard and acted upon. Expect conflicts and disagreements among stakeholders and have a well-defined conflict resolution mechanism in place. Mediation, negotiation, and compromise may be necessary to resolve conflicts. Highlight the benefits of your projects to all stakeholders. This might include economic growth, job creation, environmental protection, and technological advancement. Provide incentives for stakeholders to actively participate. The necessity of a new and dynamic framework for the legal aspects of stakeholder engagement, stakeholders rights and duties, as well as those of the projects involving them might be needed in the future.

This deliverable is to be an important guideline for future integration of stakeholders during developing sustainable blue economy, reducing ocean pollution, improving circularity and stimulating biodiversity (restoration) in our European waters. It is encouraged to use it across the different lighthouses selected in Europe.

2 Fulfilling the Mission objectives

The Mission Ocean, Seas and Waters, the new Horizon Europe Program for 2021-2027 is articulated around five missions, targeting the main challenges where research and innovation efforts should be concentrated. The Mission aims to restore our oceans, seas and waters by 2030, through the achievement of three main objectives:

- 1) Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity.
- 2) Prevent and eliminate pollution.
- 3) Make the sustainable blue economy carbon neutral and circular.

The implementation of the Mission is supported by transversal actions or “cross-cutting enablers” that will provide access to a digital ocean and water knowledge system (digital twin of the ocean) and guarantee broad public mobilisation and engagement throughout the implementation of the Mission.

The Mission goes beyond research and innovation and will create new forms of governance and ways to connect with the citizens. In its current phase, the “development and piloting” phase, that runs from 2022 to 2025, the Mission has defined “lighthouses” in each major European sea and river basin. The lighthouses are important sites that act as hubs and platforms for the development, demonstration and implementation of solutions aimed for in the Mission. Therefore, more specified targets are set per lighthouse in Europe, sometimes including more than one objective.

There are four lighthouses defined in Europe: the Danube River and Black Sea; the Atlantic and Arctic Ocean; the Mediterranean Sea; the Baltic and North Sea. The lighthouses will be complemented by enabling actions, in particular a digital ocean and water knowledge system and public mobilisation, as well as engagement and awareness.

The second phase ‘deployment and upscaling’ (2026-2030), will consist of supporting the transfer, uptake and upscale of R&I solutions developed in the first phase of the Mission, mostly through private funding.

PREP4BLUE is the first coordination and support action project of the Mission Ocean, seas and waters, with the overarching objective to facilitate a successful implementation of the first phase of the Mission Ocean & Waters (2022-2025) by developing the co-creation and co-implementation of R&I modalities required to achieve the Mission objectives, and preparing the ground for inspiring and engaging citizens and stakeholders. The project will deliver relevant recommendations and methodologies on stakeholder engagement. The project team is notably mapping and assessing multidisciplinary, multi-stakeholder strategies involving industry, public authorities, citizens, academia and associations while envisaging the natural environment as key for social innovation and to efficiently bring society closer to the ocean.

The lighthouse specific objectives are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview on specific mission ocean objectives per LH

The targets set per objective in the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 are for:

Danube river and Black sea, Atlantic and Arctic Ocean LHs

Objective: Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030:

- Protect a minimum of 30% of the EU’s sea area and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network.
- Strictly protect at least 10% of the EU’s sea area.
- Restore at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers.
- Contribute to relevant upcoming marine nature restoration targets including degraded seabed habitats and coastal ecosystems.

Mediterranean Sea LH

Objective: Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil⁴⁸:

- Reduce by at least 50% plastic litter at sea.
- Reduce by at least 30% microplastics released into the environment.
- Reduce by at least 50% nutrient losses, the use and risk of chemical pesticides.

Baltic and North Sea LH

Objective: Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy:

- Eliminate greenhouse gas emissions from maritime economic activities in the EU and sequester those emissions that cannot be avoided (net zero maritime emissions).
- Develop zero-carbon and low-impact aquaculture, and promote circular, low-carbon multi-purpose use of marine and water space.

3 Identifying stakeholders and understanding the specific interests and needs: creating a stakeholder map

3.1 Identify the relevant stakeholders for the Mission

As the penta-helix approach is used, industry/businesses, public authorities, citizens/local residents, academia/the knowledge sector and associations are considered as a base through these guidelines, but who are the key stakeholders? In the process of writing, the team of experts decided not to consider cultural relevance as a parameter to identify key methodologies to reach the mission, but to rely on the baseline studies produced by the European Commission.

Stakeholder(s) (SH) are “a person such as an employee, customer, or citizen who is involved with an organization, society, etc. and therefore has responsibilities towards it and an interest in its success”³

In the case of the Mission “Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030” a stakeholder is someone (either individual person or organisation) that has interests and/or responsibilities towards achieving the Mission’s objectives.

Olander (2007) specifies the difference between internal and external stakeholders. Internal stakeholders are those who are involved in the implementation and/or execution of a project, plan or policy, while external SHs are those who are affected by the implementation and/or execution. According to Olander’s definition, Mission stakeholders could be further split in two subgroups:

1. SH who are directly involved as partners in projects supported/funded by the Mission or actions that were submitted to the Mission charter;
2. SH that are engaged or to be engaged by such projects/actions. Therefore, given the extent of MO, all kinds of stakeholders should be considered but this prerequisite calls LHs for a strong effort as for their identification;

Stakeholder identification is an essential early step in the stakeholder engagement (SHenG) processes. The identification process can be done in several steps and/or use different identification methods either at the start of the SHenG process or throughout the engagement period.

Depending on the aim of the SHenG (What am I aiming for with engaging SH : discussions, policy making, etc.), various categories of stakeholders can be involved at different levels of involvement. The process is dynamic: Reed et al. (2009) clearly states , SH identification is an iterative process during which additional stakeholders are added while the analysis continues.

³ Sources:

- [STAKEHOLDER | English meaning - Cambridge Dictionary.](#)
- Within the theoretical framework of strategic management, all definitions are based on Freeman (1984), where a stakeholder is described as 'the group and/or individuals who are affected by an organisation's objectives'.

Depending on the topics addressed during the SHenG, please find some general entities and topics that can be of relevance within a Mission Ocean context⁴:

- NGOs,
- maritime sectors : Aquaculture and fish farming, Commercial transport, Ports, Fisheries, Extraction of minerals, Marine renewable energy, Coastal protection, Nature inclusive design, Recreational activities , Leisure navigation, Ocean pollution reduction etc.;
- state administrations;
- local authorities;
- technical bodies : Marine Protected Areas Agencies, Consultancy offices, etc.

The first list of SH to be engaged is based on initial knowledge of the researchers, consultants and locals. That holistic knowledge can be based on previous interactions with the different SH in previous SHenG or any other process and/or involvement in various networks. Another way of initiating a first list is to investigate grey literature (e.g. annual reports, newsletters, local news journals, websites, etc.) and peer-reviewed literature and to list all the SH that appear in those.

Once a first list of categories or stakeholders to be engaged is made based on knowledge of the environment or various networks, it should be expanded. This initial type of sampling is known as prism sampling⁵. Sometimes stakeholders on the list “to be engaged/involved” are not available or do not want to be involved. That is why it is important to have substitutes. If the initial list is not sufficient, it can be expanded by snowball sampling⁶. Snowball sampling is a method using an initial list of stakeholders and ask them to suggest names of other people and/or organisations who should be involved in the SHenG.

Next to prism and snowball sampling, the two main methods, there are many other alternatives for identifying the relevant stakeholders. For example: expert interviews, media, social media, written records, focus groups, group brainstorming, relationship attributes (Mitchell, 1997), value management workshops, desktop studies, etc⁷.

⁴ Nys, C., Bailly, D. 2018. Methodology guide for semi-structured interviews. EU Project Grant No.: EASME/EMFF/2015/1.2.1.3/03/SI2.742089. Supporting Implementation of Marine Spatial Planning in the Northern European Atlantic Region (SIMNORAT). Université de Bretagne Occidentale. 20p. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.25111.68002

⁵ Prism sampling: we start with the sample obtained empirically and considered "as best we can", and we consider that this sample is representative of a population whose characteristics we do not know about beforehand (Source: Martin, O., 2012. *L'analyse quantitative des données: L'enquête et ses méthodes 3rd ed. F. de Singly, ed., Paris: Armand Colin.*)

⁶ Snowball sampling: Method using a group of initial stakeholders to suggest names of other people or groups of people who are eligible for the study. (Source: Atkinson, R. & Flint, J., 2004. *Snowball Sampling. Encyclopedia of Social Science Research Methods*, pp.1044–1045. / Morgan, D., 2008. *Snowball sampling. The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*, pp.816–817.).

⁷ Olunde et al., 2021 (<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/FEBE-05-2021-0023/full/pdf?title=stakeholder-identification-methods-used-in-private-organisations-projects-in-nigeria>); Karlsen, 2022 (https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jan-Karlsen-5/publication/228934223_Project_Stakeholder_Management/links/609291a1458515d315f8e900/Project-Stakeholder-Management.pdf); Chevalier & Buckles, 2008 (<https://idl-bnc-idrc.dspacedirect.org/bitstream/handle/10625/35977/IDL-35977.pdf?sequence=1>)

Which stakeholders are needed to stimulate research and innovation for carbon neutrality and circularity at sea, protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, and to avoid pollution at sea?

Which stakeholders are to be included in the guidelines, i.e., the most relevant stakeholders to engage with the mission?

For that, the penta-helix structure of industry and businesses, science, public authorities (policy makers), citizens and associations is considered, and some extension. It must be underlined that there is an overlap in both considerations, citizen and stakeholder engagement (5-helix) – as all considered are also citizens.

The priority stakeholders' categories are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Stakeholder categories relevant per MO target

TARGET Mission Ocean	Citizen	Science	CSO	Policy	Industry/innovative business
Protect a minimum of 30% of the EU's sea area and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network.		x	x	x	
Strictly protect at least 10% of the EU's sea area.		x	x	x	
Restore at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers.	x	x	x	x	x
Contribute to relevant upcoming marine nature restoration targets including degraded seabed habitats and coastal ecosystems.		x	x	x	x
Reduce by at least 50% plastic litter at sea.	x	x	x	x	x
Reduce by at least 30% microplastics released into the environment.	x	x	x	x	x
Reduce by at least 50% nutrient losses, the use and risk of chemical pesticides.				x	x
Eliminate greenhouse gas emissions from maritime economic activities in the EU and sequester those emissions that cannot be avoided (net zero maritime emissions).		x		x	x
Develop zero-carbon and low-impact aquaculture, and promote circular, low-carbon multi-purpose use of marine and water space.		x		x	x

Once the categories of SH to be involved are defined, it's important to be more precise and look locally at those SH and list them on a local or regional level by their name and/or organization. This can be done by using a mix of empirical knowledge, literature (both grey and peer-reviewed), direct contact and by using snowball sampling as explained above. In the case of the Mission, this is also done/helped

by using the baseline studies about each of the lighthouses as a starting point, as stimulated below. Additionally, the Mission Implementation Plan⁸ stresses how the lighthouses have been launched:

- “to mobilise potential partners, Member States, regions, multilateral organisations and other relevant actors, to address common challenges collectively” (one of the key mandates of the Mission will be to promote basin-wide cooperation, commitment and deployment of solutions addressing the Mission’s objectives).
- “to develop a multi-level partnership to be directly involved in the Mission implementation and governance (undertaking R&I activities, scaling up innovations, developing innovative products and services, new business models, etc.).
- “to deliver a dynamic investment ecosystem based on a wide array of funding sources (public, public-private, and private) and financial and non-financial instruments”.

To this end, LHs are built

- on *“existing commitments and initiatives and create synergies with basin level governance structures already in place”* (prism sampling) for coordinating, stimulating synergies and assuring consistency with and between regional/national initiatives but also
- for *“supporting the active participation of regions, macro-regions, associations of regions and communities as well as other stakeholders in the Mission”* thanks to the national structures that Member States and Region have put in place (snowball sampling).
- *”to put in place a community of interested impact investors and philanthropic donors as well as EU/Transnational programmes, Member States investment and other specific initiatives in providing co-funding”*.

This led to the identification of the following categories of stakeholders to be engaged:

1. Governmental institutions,
2. R&D and innovation entities,
3. Industry and business grouping and networks,
4. NGOs and civil society organisations,
5. Philanthropic organisations,
6. Financial institutions.

With this expansion of the categories and within such categories, specific SH were identified according to the following 4 criteria and the relation to the Mission:

1. High political importance to cooperate with the EC/Mission secretariat on the implementation of the Mission.
2. Experience in the topics aligned with the Mission objectives implemented in each lighthouse area.
3. Efficiency, effectiveness, and potential scalability of the organizations and the potential of their involvement in Mission implementation
4. High potential of collaboration with the Mission Implementation.

As for this last one criteria “high potential of collaboration with the Mission Implementation”, the experts decided to further organize the SHs by the following 5 categories:

⁸ European Commission. (2021). Implementation plan mission ocean - https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-09/ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_for_publication.pdf

- **Political partner:** organizations with political influence that are key for the European Commission to be able to achieve results in the lighthouse areas as well as to increase the impact and outreach of the Mission.
- **Decision makers:** organizations/authorities with the power to decide on policy issues and on approving small and large-scale projects (national and regional institutions).
- **Financing/programming partner:** organizations that could partner with the European Commission to provide financing for the development of projects and activities to reach the Mission’s objectives;
- **Science partner:** focused on science, research, development, innovation.
- **Potential project leader:** organizations that are already working “on the ground” in the area (are leading specific projects) that could potentially serve as partners to realize concrete projects for the European Commission.

PREP4BLUE analysed the workplan 2021-2022 and 2022-2023 for identifying the general SHs to be engaged by LHs according to their specific objectives. P4B considered also the best methods for part of the goals of the Mission. Increased awareness of stakeholders and citizens about the Mission’s objectives, programmes and tools, and about the possibilities for their contribution to the mission, as well as improved access of stakeholders (scientific community, businesses, local and regional communities, NGOs and others) to programmes and instruments supporting restoration, conservation and sustainable use of the ocean, seas and waters.

Please consult Table 3 “Stakeholders (categories) to be involved per lighthouse and/or objective in the Mission Work program 2021-2022”.

Table 3. Stakeholders (categories) to be involved per lighthouse and/or objective in the Mission Work program 2021-2022

Danube	Atlantic & Arctic	Mediterranean	North & Baltic
citizen science	accelerators	citizens to civil society, SMEs and other businesses	algae cultures, oysters, conchicultures, shrimps
conservationists	coastal communities	Collectivities	Aquaculture farms
data researchers, companies, national agencies	construction, contractors, urban planners, policies, townhalls	controlling mechanism, protocols	aquaculture industry
European Volunteer Corps and Mission Citizen Assemblies	consultancies	engineers	aquaculture industry
Farming	Consultancies, construction companies, risk prevention local authorities, urban planners, architects	Farming	consumers
local businesses, cooperatives	EU Outermost Regions	fishing industry	energy
local communities	European volunteer/solidarity corps and citizens science activities in the restoration activities	from young innovators to start-ups	fishing

management bodies	fishing, industry, wastewater treatment, ports, farming, cities	Industry	fishing community
managers of protected areas	Joint Research Centre	Entrepreneurs	governmental controllers and protocols
mediators, territorial concertation experts, trainers, management bodies, NGOs	knowledge share platform owners	Landfills	leisure,
national authorities for natural risk prevention	local actors and communities in active and passive marine ecosystem restoration	local/regional	marine sports, leisure, port constructions, sewage, port police, fishing
NGOs, conservationists	oyster cultures, aquacultures, algacultures	management bodies	maritime transport, marine sports, leisure, port constructions, sewage, port police, fishing
Ocean literacy networks	research and Innovation	Municipalities	NGOs
regional and local authorities from the 'associated regions'	SMEs, oceanographic businesses, research, NGOs, local authorities	policy makers	port constructions,
SMEs, investors and other business stakeholders		policy makers	port police,
SRIA Black Sea		Recycling	sewage,
wastewater treatment plants, research, policies, controllers		recycling subcontractors	sustainable regenerative farming
water purification plans, water agencies		Researchers	Trainers and mediators
Water4All Partnership and Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership	project partnership	SMEs	
		social entrepreneurship	
		waste treatment	

The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook (2008)⁹, providing best practice guidelines for stakeholder engagement in research projects on biodiversity and ecosystem services' shows that in the process of identifying stakeholders, it is important to check for your project:

- who is responsible for decision making,
- who is being affected, who is interested,
- who has received previous engagement,

⁹ <https://www.biodiversa.eu/research-funding/guides-capacity-building/stakeholder-engagement-handbook/>

- who is crucial to deliver long term results,
- and who are the most interested/relevant organisations for your work.

As an important side note: while defining the SH roles and contributions, the timing to involve them is equally important and should already be considered.

- Before the project start, if they are relevant during the developing strategy (to define concept and, identify outcomes);
- during the project: in helping establishing agreements, for resources provision, to define project planning, for training and capacity building, to help share knowledge, for the scenario development, to co-design conflict resolution and review success measurement;
- or after the (in this case research) project to define and develop how you want to implement, publicize and promote the results.

It is fundamental to plan the engagement early on.

3.2 Create a stakeholder map relevant for the Mission

Once segmentation is done, the stakeholders can be mapped to visualise the stakeholder ecosystem. Stakeholder mapping is the visual process of laying out all the stakeholders of a product, project, or idea on one map. The main benefit of a stakeholder map is to get a visual representation of all the people who can influence your project and how they are connected.

By crossing PREP4BLUE stakeholder categories per lighthouse with those identified by the baseline studies and by enriching them with the information collected, in the preliminary phases, by LH CSAs, a first map of SH could be produced:

Arctic

- Private organisations:
 - International/European: Arctic Economic Council (AEC); Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators (AECO);
- Philanthropic organisations: Prince Albert II of Monaco Foundation (FPA2);
- Financial Institutions : Nordic Investment Bank (NIB), Nordic Environment Finance Corporation (NEFCO)
- Science/R&D:
 - International/European: Arctic Frontiers Network of Policy, Business and Science; Arctic Circle Network of corporations, organisations, research institutions, and governmental bodies; University of the Arctic (uArctic); International Arctic Science Committee (IASC); EU Polar Net
- Public organisations:
 - International/European: Arctic Council; Barents-Euro Arctic Council (BEAC); Barents Regional Council; Nordic Council of Ministers; Nordic Council; Northern Dimension Policy
 - Denmark (DK): Foreign Affairs Ministry; Climate, Energy and Utilities Ministry; Environment and Food Ministry; Higher Education and Science Ministry; Industry, Business and Financial Affairs Ministry;
 - Faroe Islands (FO/DK): Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Culture; Ministry of Environment, Industry and Trade, Ministry of Fisheries;
 - Greenland (GL/DK):
 - Foreign Affairs, Business and Trade Ministry; Fisheries and Hunting Ministry; Education, Culture, Sports and Church Ministry; Ministry for Agriculture, Self-sufficiency, Energy and Environment;
 - Iceland (IS): Foreign Affairs Ministry; Culture and Business Affairs Ministry; Food, Agriculture and Fisheries Ministry; Higher Education, Science and Innovation Ministry; Environment, Energy and Climate Ministry;
 - Norway (NO): Foreign Affairs Ministry; Local Government and Regional Development Ministry; Trade, Industry and Fisheries Ministry; Climate and Environment Ministry; Ministry of Education and Research;

- NGO(s) & Associations:
 - International/European:
 - Arctic Indigenous Peoples Organisations (Aleut International Association – AIA, Arctic Ath’baskan Council – AAC, Gwich’in Council International – GCI, Inuit Circumpolar Association – ICC, Russian Association of Indigenous Peoples of the North – RAIPON, Saami Council); Sami Parliament of Norway; WWF Arctic Programme; Greenpeace; Bellona Foundation; Clean Arctic Alliance;
- Citizens

Atlantic

- Private organisations:
 - France (FR):
 - Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique – PMBA; Cluster Maritime Français (CMF)
 - Spain (ES):
 - Sustainable Ventures;
 - Portugal (PT):
 - Forum Oceano
- Science/R&D:
 - France (FR):
 - Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique – PMBA; Ifremer; CNRS;
 - Ireland (IE):
 - Marine Institute;
 - Spain (ES):
 - Fundacion Biodiversidad (Pleamar Programme); Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO); AZTI;
 - Portugal (PT):
 - CNF (Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas); Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera (IPMA);
- Public organisations:
 - International / European :
 - OSPAR; JPI Oceans; Atlantic Action Plan /Atlantic Strategy Committee; CPMRAtlantic Arc Commission;
 - France (FR):
 - Office Français pour la Biodiversité; Conservatoire du Littoral et des rivages Lacustres;
 - Ireland (IE):
 - Environmental Protection Agency – EPA;
 - Spain (ES):
 - Dirección General de Sostenibilidad de la Costa y del Mar – DGSCM; Subdirección General para la Protección del Mar – SGPM; Ministry for Ecological Transition – MITECO; Autonomous Communities and Autonomous Cities;
 - Portugal (PT):
 - Direção Geral dos Recursos Naturais, Segurança e Serviços Marítimos – DGRM; Ministerio do Mar; Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas – ICNF;
- NGO(s) & Associations:
 - International/Europe :
 - Atlantic Cities Association;

- France (FR):
Tara Ocean Foundation; Réserves Naturelles de France (RNF); Ocean and Climate Platform (OCP/POC); WWF France; Ligue pour la Protection des Oiseaux (LPO);
- Spain (ES):
WWF Spain; SEO Birdlife; Pong Pesca;
- Citizens
- Philanthropic organisations: TotalEnergies Foundation (FR);
- Financial Institutions : Foundation de France (FR); French National Research Agency (FR); JPI; Belmont Forum;

Danube

- Private organisations / Industry and business:
 - International/European : Viadonau;
 - Bosnia and Herzegovina (BA):
 - Bulgaria (BG): Marine Cluster Bulgaria;
- Science/R&D:
 - International/European : International Association for Danube Research (IAD);
 - Austria (AT): University of natural resources and life sciences (BOKU);
 - Germany (DE): Chair of Hydraulic and Water Resources engineering of the University of Romania (RO): Danube Delta National Institute for Research and Development (DDNI)
 - Serbia (RS): Jaroslav Černi Water Institute
 - Slovenia (SI): Institute for Water of the Republic of Slovenia (iZVRS);
- Public organisations:
 - International/European : International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River (ICDPR); Commission on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution (BSC); Lower Danube Green Corridor;
 - Austria (AT): Federal Ministry for Agriculture, Regions and Tourism
 - Bosnia and Herzegovina (BA): Federal Ministry of Physical Planning and Environment; Autonomous cantons (10); Ministry for Urbanism, Construction, Communal Issues and Ecology (Republika Srpska);
 - Bulgaria (BG): Ministry of Environment and Water; Directorate National Office for Protection of Nature;
 - Croatia (HR): Hrvatske Vode (Croatian Waters); Ministry of Environmental Protection and Energy (Directorate for Water Management);
 - Czech Republic (CZ): Ministry for Agriculture; Ministry of Environment;
 - Germany (DE): Federal Ministry for the Environment; Länder Ministries; Ministry of the Environment, Climate Protection and the Energy sector of Baden-Württemberg; Bavarian State Ministry of the Environment and Consumer Protection;
 - Hungary (HU): Ministry of the Interior; General Directorate of Water Management; Ministry of Agriculture;
 - Republic of Moldova (MD): Ministry of Ecology, Construction and Territorial Development; Ministry of Agriculture, Regional Development and Environment;
 - Montenegro (ME): Ministry of Ecology, Spatial Planning and Urbanism;
 - Romania (RO): Romanian Waters (National Administration); Ministry of the Environment, Waters and Forests;

- Serbia (RS): Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management; Ministry of Environmental Protection;
- Slovakia (SK): Ministry of Environment;
- Slovenia (SI): Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning;
- Ukraine (UA): Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources;
- NGO(s) & Associations:
 - International/European: IUCN; WWF; Birdlife international; Nature Conservancy (TNC); Rewilding Europe;
- Citizens
- Philanthropic organisations: Coca-Cola Foundation;
- Financial Institutions : European Investment Bank; Global Environment Facility (GEF); UNDP; World Bank Group;

Mediterranean

- Science/R&D:
 - International/European: EFARO - European Fisheries and Aquaculture Research Organisations, UNIMED – Mediterranean University Union, BlueMed Initiative, Mediterranean Science Commission (CIESM), Center for Mediterranean Integration (CMI), European Marine Board;
 - Spain (ES): Institute of Marine Research - Spanish National Research Council, University of Jaén, CSIC - Institut de Ciències del Mar, Universidad de Murcia, AIMPLAS - Technological Institute of Plastics;
 - Portugal (PT): Universidade do Algarve, CIIMAR – Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research, Network of Chemistry and Technology (REQUIMTE);
 - Italy (IT): National Research Council of Italy (CNR), CORILA - Consorzio per il Coordinamento delle Ricerche Inerenti al Sistema Lagunare di Venezia, SciNMeet - Italian Oceanographic Commission, Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna, Università Politecnica Delle Marche, Università di Siena;
 - France (FR): Institut français de recherche pour l'exploitation de la mer (Ifremer); CNRS;
 - Greece (GR): Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR), International Center for Research on the Environment and the Economy;
 - Croatia (HR): University of Split, Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries (IOF);
 - Malta: Università Ta Malta;
 - Turkey: Middle East Technical University (METU) - Institute of Marine Sciences;
 - Tunisia: Institut National des Sciences et Technologies de la Mer;
- Private organisations / Industry and business:

- International/European:
 - European Aquaculture Technology and Innovation Platform (EATiP), EUROPECHE, FARM EUROPE NETWORK, MEDAC, BUSINESSMED (Union of Mediterranean Confederations of Enterprises), Mediterranean World Economic Foresight Institute – IPEMED, Plastics Europe association;
 - Serbia: JUPLAS, Plastics Europe association;
 - Turkey: PAGEV Plastics Europe association;
 - Albania: APKA Plastics Europe association;
 - Bosnia Herzegovina: KFBih Plastics Europe association;
 - Greece: AHPI Plastics Europe association, ELIME-Hellenic port association,;
 - Croatia: HKG Plastics Europe association;
 - Italy: Federchimica PlasticsEurope; BIG, Italian BLUEGROWTH Technology Cluster
 - Egypt: EPEMA, Plastics Europe association;
 - Marocco: FMP, Plastics Europe association ;
 - Tunisia: Chambre Syndicale des Industriels du Plastique c/o UTICA;
 - France: Board Bureau International des Containers ;
 - Portugal: FORUM OCEANO, Portuguese bluegrowth cluster;
 - Belgium: Blue Cluster;
- Public organisations:
 - International/European:
 - Mediterranean Commission on Sustainable Development (MCSD), UNEP MAP, UNION FOR MEDITERRANEAN, WestMED Initiative, Coalition for an exemplary Mediterranean in 2030, International Maritime Organization (IMO), the Regional Marine Pollution Emergency Response Centre for the Mediterranean Sea (REMPEC), European Environmental Agency, EUSAIR, COPPEM -Permanent committee of the Euro-MED local authorities and regions, ARLEM- Euro-Mediterranean regional and local assembly and EU COMMITTEE OF THE REGION, International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean – GFCM, Global Programme of Action for the Protection of the Marine Environment from Land- based Activities (GPA), Intermediterranean Commission of the Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions (CPMR), MedCities, WAREG - Association of European Regulators, ;
 - Italy (IT):
 - Ministry of Ecological Transition – MiTE, Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research – ISPRA, ENEA - Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile; Italian Alliance for Sustainable Development (ASviS), Agenzia Regionale per la Protezione Dell'Ambiente (ARPA), Autorità di Sistema Portuale;
 - France (FR):
 - Ministry of Ecological Transition, Territory Cohesion State Secretary in charge of the Sea, Agency for Sustainable Mediterranean Cities and Territories (AVITEM);
 - Croatia (HR):
 - Ministry of Environmental Protection, Energy Ministry of Regional Development, EU Funds Croatian Waters (Hrvatske Vode) - national water management agency;
 - Cyprus:
 - Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment, Nicosia Development Agency (ANEL);
 - Greece:

Ministry for the Environment, Physical Planning and Public Works, Ministry of Maritime Affairs, Islands and Fisheries, Ministry of Regional Development and Competitiveness;

- Malta:
Ministry for the Environment, Energy and Enterprise (MEEE), Energy and Water Agency;
- Slovenia:
Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning
- Spain:
Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO), Casa Mediterráneo
- NGO(s) & Associations:
 - International/Europe:
World Ocean Council Europe, IUCN Centre for Mediterranean Cooperation (IUCN-MED), Posidonia Green Project, WWF Mediterranean Marine Initiative, Mediterranean Information Office for Environment, Culture and Sustainable Development (MIO-ECSDE), Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA Foundation), Prince Albert II of Monaco Foundation, Med Fund, European Plastic Pirates initiative, MIO-ECSDE - Mediterranean Information Office for the Environment, Culture and Sustainable Development;
 - Italy: (IT):
Venice Lagoon Plastic Free, Marevivo, Chimica Verde Bionet;
 - Spain (ES):
SUBMON, Clean Boating Movement;
 - France (FR):
Project Rescue Ocean, Fundacion Philippe Cousteau, Tara Ocean Foundation, Innovations Bleues;
 - Albania (AL):
Co-PLAN – Institute for Habitat Development
 - Cyprus:
Let's Make Cyprus Green
- Citizens

Baltic-North Sea (BANOS)

- Private Organizations:
 - Maersk Group
 - Stena Line
 - Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy
 - Fiskano
 - Skretting
 - Nordic Tankers
 - IKEA
 - Neste
 - Ecohz
 - Blue Cluster

- **Philanthropic Organizations:**
 - Baltic Sea Action Group (BSAG): Focuses on improving the ecological state of the Baltic Sea, particularly addressing agricultural runoff.
 - The Ocean Cleanup: Works on cleaning up plastic pollution globally, indirectly benefiting marine environments.
 - The Swedish Postcode Foundation: Supports various environmental initiatives, including marine conservation.
 - The MAVA Foundation: Funds projects related to marine conservation and sustainable fisheries.
 - Prince Albert II of Monaco Foundation: Supports global environmental projects, including those focused on marine conservation.
 - Baltic Sea 2020: Works on projects to reduce eutrophication and improve the health of the Baltic Sea.
 - The Baltic Sea Fund: Supports initiatives that address environmental challenges in the Baltic Sea region.
 - Oceans 5: A global fund that supports initiatives for marine conservation, including in the North Sea.
 - The Sylvia Earle Alliance/Mission Blue: Advocates for the protection of marine environments globally.
 - Waitt Foundation: Supports sustainable fishing practices and marine conservation projects.
- **Financial Institutions:**
 - European Investment Bank (EIB)
 - KfW Development Bank
 - Nordic Investment Bank (NIB)
 - Swedbank
 - Danske Bank
 - SEB Bank
 - Norges Bank Investment Management (NBIM)
 - European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)
 - DNB ASA
 - Swedish National Pension Funds
- **Public Bodies:**
 - Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management (HaV),
 - Flemish Institute for the Sea (VLIZ)
 - German Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH): Oversees activities impacting the North Sea, contributing to conservation efforts,
 - Danish Environmental Protection Agency: Implements environmental policies for the protection of the marine environment,
 - Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE)
 - European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)
 - The Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (HELCOM)
 - Maritime and Coastguard Agency (UK)
 - Norwegian Environment Agency
 - Environmental Protection Agency of Lithuania
 - Maritime Administration of Latvia

- NGOs:
 - Oceana Europe: Advocates for policies ensuring the restoration and sustainable management of European seas.
 - Baltic Sea Centre: Conducts research and provides expertise on environmental issues affecting the Baltic Sea.
 - Clean Baltic Sea: A project by the John Nurminen Foundation, focusing on reducing nutrient loads in the Baltic Sea.
 - BirdLife International - European Division: Works on the conservation of seabirds and their habitats in the Baltic and North Sea.
 - Friends of the Earth Europe: Advocates for policies promoting environmental sustainability and addressing human impact on marine ecosystems.
 - Baltic Sea Foundation: Works on projects addressing environmental challenges in the Baltic Sea.
 - Coalition Clean Baltic: A network of NGOs working on various environmental issues affecting the Baltic Sea.
 - Green Belt Movement: Advocates for environmental conservation and sustainable development globally.
 - World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) Baltic: Works on projects for the conservation and sustainable use of natural resources in the Baltic Sea.
 - Marine Conservation Society (MCS): Works on marine conservation issues, including those affecting the North Sea

Online tool to support stakeholder mapping in the context of stakeholder engagement.

Wavelinks is an interactive web platform developed jointly by three CSA projects under the Mission Ocean: PREP4BLUE, BlueMissionBANOS and BlueMissionAA. The platform can be found at the following address: www.wavelinks.eu. Wavelinks is meant to play a crucial role in mapping and supporting the research and innovation ecosystem associated with the Mission Ocean. It ambitions to act as a catalyst for fostering collaborations, seamlessly connecting academia, industry, and society to enhance the impact of projects and initiatives working towards the objectives of the Mission Ocean and Waters.. Tailored for anyone engaged with or interested in the Mission Ocean, Wavelinks is an essential tool for staying informed about the latest developments in sustainable blue projects. It facilitates new connections between projects and stakeholders and allows its users to explore in depth projects, stakeholders, stakeholder engagement methods and citizen science initiatives in the Mission Ocean ecosystem.

Table 4. Online support tool available on wavelinks

Online tool to support stakeholder mapping in the context of stakeholder engagement.

[WaveLinks](#) notably includes a database of organizations that participate on projects linked to the Mission Ocean that can be considered as a database of stakeholders of the Mission Ocean. This database of stakeholders can be visualized, searched, and filtered by users of the online tool. User will for example be able to search for stakeholders that participate(d) in projects related to the keyword “microalgae” or “MPAs”. Users will also be able to search specifically for stakeholders who participate(d) in projects linked to the Objective 3 of the Mission Ocean. The interlinkages between the project, participant and stakeholder methods data will also allow users to look for all stakeholders who have used a given stakeholder engagement method in the past. In this way Wave Links can support users to identify potential stakeholder to engage.

In the next version of the SHEM online tool, we will identify the stakeholders that have been engaged by a given method in past projects (when this information is available in the deliverables of the project or when this information is given by users inputting new data in the database). The stakeholders engaged in the past by a given method will be displayed on the detail page of this method.

3.3 Specific stakeholder interests and needs per category of stakeholder operating in the lighthouses area in the Mission

The Mission underscores the importance of achieving substantial, far-reaching results and impacts, underscoring the need for an overarching governance structure that can effectively set down cooperation among a wide spectrum of stakeholders, all of whom share a wide interest in advancing the mission’s ambitious objectives. Within the scope of its mandate, the Mission assumes a the main role in advocating for, and subsequently enabling, basin-wide collaboration. It strives to safeguard commitment among stakeholders and spearhead the active implementation of innovative solutions. When designing a specific project, it is important to choose the relevant organisations listed below for the project as well as to prioritise them. In general, categories, needs, challenges and interests per category are listed in the sections below (from 3.3.1 to 3.3.8), this is to be considered according to the criteria one defines for his or her project.

According to ‘BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook (2008)’¹⁰, providing best practice guidelines for stakeholder engagement in research projects on biodiversity and ecosystem services’, desktop research, the baseline studies, several expert consultations and empirical knowledge, an attempt to defining interests and needs per stakeholder category was made. This is list is not all-compassing and limited, but it provides a good overview in who to contact should you be involved in an activity or project related to the mission.

¹⁰ <https://www.biodiversa.eu/research-funding/guides-capacity-building/stakeholder-engagement-handbook/>

3.3.1 Interest and needs of governments and policy makers

Needs

1. Need for adequate data for decision-making.

To make informed decisions, governments require extensive, reliable, and timely data. Governments may create policies that directly address current challenges with reliable facts rather than making assumptions. Governments can more efficiently distribute resources, both human and financial, if they know where the greatest need exists. Data serves as a starting point (or baseline) for measuring progress. Regular data updates aid in the monitoring of changes throughout time, allowing governments to assess the success of their initiatives. Adequate data helps governments to anticipate and analyse possible hazards, whether they are environmental, economic, or social in nature, also related to the blue economy.

Type of data required in Mission related projects:

Environmental metrics (e.g. water quality, biodiversity counts, pollution levels, habitat health, marine (protected) species), socio-economic data, economic data and ramifications, *etc.* Economic ramifications as understanding the economic impact of marine degradation on fisheries or tourism, can be a strong motivator for government action and cultural and historical information to ensure policies respect and preservation of traditional marine practice. For example, data on nitrogen or carbon capture can help advocating for a sustainable blue economy for example via multi-use and nature inclusive design.

2. Need for Funding:

Governments often need both internal budget allocations and external funding sources, like grants or international aid, to support their initiatives. Governments are faced with the task of balancing numerous requirements. The distribution frequently reflects a country's urgent difficulties as well as its long-term ambitions. It is the aim of the Mission Oceans to at least invest in a sustainable blue economy

- **Internal fundings.**
Governments distribute money for several industries each year. Environmental programmes receive a share of this funding based on their importance among other pressing needs such as healthcare, infrastructure, and education. Governments may raise funding for marine restoration by levying eco-taxes, such as fees on plastic use, carbon emissions, or sectors with a substantial environmental effect. Some countries have sovereign wealth funds or other types of financial reserves. Parts of these funds can be used to fund environmental initiatives and sustainable economies based on national goals.
- **External fundings.**
Numerous international organisations, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), foundations, and charitable organisations provide funding for environmental protection. International aid can be either bilateral (one country directly offers financial assistance to another, often in conjunction with larger diplomatic or trade agreements) or multilateral (funds pooled by multiple countries and distributed through international organisations such as the United Nations, World Bank, or regional development banks).
Public-commercial Partnerships (PPPs) are joint initiatives between governments and commercial companies. Private companies contribute finance, technology, and knowledge, while governments give regulatory oversight, access, and possible tax breaks.
Crowdfunding for certain initiatives, particularly those with global relevance or appeal, governments (sometimes in partnership with NGOs) may use crowdfunding platforms to gather modest sums of money from a big number of individuals throughout the world.

3. **Need for legislative support:**

In order to put more environmentally sustainable policies into action, governments require backing in legislative bodies to pass necessary laws or amendments. Furthermore, legislation establishes a lasting framework, which can endure beyond transient government terms, making it crucial for long-term initiatives such as environmental conservation.

4. **International cooperation.**

The vast expanse of our planet's oceans and numerous water systems go beyond national borders, making global collaboration indispensable. When addressing challenges like pollution removal, restoring marine ecosystems, or transitioning to a sustainable blue-economy, isolated actions by individual nations might fall short. Coordinated international efforts ensure that policies and actions in one country reinforce, rather than undermine, those in another. By pooling resources, expertise, and technological advancements, nations can collectively accelerate the transition to a carbon-neutral blue-economy. Furthermore, shared global frameworks and agreements can set universally accepted benchmarks, driving nations to adopt sustainable practices and prioritize the health of our shared waters. Therefore, it is also of uttermost importance to promote multi-use and reduce this way transport impact and material use.

Interests:

1. **Economic growth.**

Vibrant and thriving oceans and waterways are more than just ecological treasures; they are economic powerhouses. A rejuvenated marine ecosystem means abundant fish stocks, which directly bolsters the fisheries sector. Beyond that, pristine beaches, clear waters, and marine protected areas attract tourists from around the world, injecting life into the tourism industry. Additionally, activities such as shipping, aquaculture, and even emerging sectors like marine biotechnology, rely on clean and healthy oceans. Energy and thriving alternative energy sectors are a must to achieve the Energy production targets. Investing is a strategic move to ensure sustainable economic growth and job creation in these vital sectors.

2. **Environmental conservation.**

By conserving the environment, we're not only protecting a delicate balance but also preserving the awe-inspiring beauty of nature that has inspired poets, artists, and thinkers for generations. Combining the (blue) economy in a holistic and sustainable way allows for the best balance between economic growth, wellbeing and environmental protection. Combining several sea uses as well as nature inclusive design is one way of doing so.

3. **Social well-being.**

The intrinsic relationship between humans and their surrounding environment is evident in the manifold ways oceans and waterways touch our daily lives. Clean waters are essential for public health; they reduce the risk of waterborne diseases and ensure safer seafood consumption. Additionally, millions globally depend on marine ecosystems for their livelihoods, be it through fishing, tourism, or other related industries. A thriving marine environment also means recreational spaces for families, offering both physical and mental health benefits. Governments, in recognising the multifaceted role of clean oceans and waterways, understand that their conservation is not just an environmental priority but a pivotal strategy to foster a happier, healthier, and more cohesive society, optimally benefitting from ecosystem services as well as through energy and food supply.

Table 5. Examples of engagement Strategies for governments and policy makers

Engagement Strategies (some examples)

- Regular stakeholder meetings: organizing recurrent dialogues with pertinent governmental entities and policymakers offers a mechanism to consistently apprise them of advancements, hindrances, and emerging prospects. Such meetings form the bedrock of symbiotic relationships, allowing for real-time feedback, ensuring alignment with national or regional priorities, and aiding in mutual goal-setting.
- Data sharing platforms: the inception of centralized platforms for data assimilation and dissemination plays a main role in the modern digital landscape. These platforms not only streamline access to critical information but also enhance its interpretability. By providing an aggregated space where data can be deciphered and harnessed, it equips policymakers with robust empirical evidence, facilitating informed policy drafting and adjustments. The relevance of the cross-cutting enabler ‘Digital ocean and water knowledge system: digital twin’ is herewith underlined. Today, EMODNET is the database/platform example.
- Collaborative projects: by forging strategic alliances with governmental bodies on particular ventures, philanthropic entities can capitalize on the established infrastructure and resources of the state. This synergy amplifies the reach and impact of initiatives, ensuring that interventions are not just theoretically sound but also practically feasible and grounded in the local context.
- International summits: playing an active role in, or even spearheading, global symposiums provides a platform to transcend national boundaries, fostering collaborative spirit among nations. These summits serve as melting pots of innovative solutions, shared challenges, and best practices, offering participants a holistic view and enabling the derivation of strategies that are both globally informed and locally relevant. Some examples are the launching of the lighthouses and the Mission Annual Forum.
- Awareness campaigns: by orchestrating campaigns that consistently spotlight the mission's tenets and achievements, there's an opportunity to shape public perception and garner widespread support. Such public endorsement, especially in democratic settings, can act as a catalyst, nudging policymakers towards favourable action, given the evident alignment with their constituents' sentiments.
- Policy recommendations: offering meticulously researched policy advisories, underpinned by concrete data, bridges the gap between empirical research and legislative action. By presenting such recommendations, philanthropic entities can act as thought leaders, aiding governmental bodies in sculpting effective, data-driven legal frameworks and strategic blueprints.

Below are some concrete examples of additional categories:

International Decision-Making Bodies:

- a. United Nations Frameworks:
 - UN Oceans: an inter-agency collaboration mechanism that seeks to enhance the coordination and coherence of UN System activities related to ocean and coastal areas.

- Sustainable Development Goal 14 (SDG 14): "Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development." This goal serves as a guiding post for international initiatives on ocean conservation.
 - b. International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN): provides public, private, and non-governmental organizations with knowledge and tools that enable human progress, economic development, and nature conservation to take place together.
 - c. World Bank's Ocean Partnerships: engages in projects that link finance to demand for good ocean governance.
- 2. Regional Decision-Making Bodies:**
- a. OSPAR Commission (for the Northeast Atlantic): cooperation for the protection and conservation of the Northeast Atlantic and its resources.
 - b. HELCOM (Baltic Sea): protects the marine environment of the Baltic Sea from all sources of pollution.
 - c. Regional Seas Conventions: UNEP-sponsored regional collaboration frameworks such as the Mediterranean Action Plan, the Action Plan for the Protection and Sustainable Development of the Marine Environment of the Northwest Pacific Region, etc.
- 3. National and Sub-National Decision-Making Bodies:**
- a. National Ministries and Departments: most countries have specific ministries or departments dedicated to environment, fisheries, and water resources. These are the primary bodies setting policies and regulations for the preservation of oceans and water within national boundaries.
 - b. Coastal Management Bodies: entities responsible for managing and protecting the coastal zones and their ecosystems.
 - c. National Research and Monitoring Institutions: they provide data, monitoring services, and feedback loops necessary to evaluate and adjust national strategies and policies related to water and oceans.
- 4. Entities Relevant to MSFD and WFD:**
- a. Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD): an EU directive that aims for good environmental status of the EU's marine waters by 2020 and beyond. It involves coordinated monitoring and measures across member states.
 - b. Water Framework Directive (WFD): it's an EU directive aiming for a holistic "river basin" approach for inland waters. It covers several water management aspects, including chemical status, ecological status, and environmental flow requirements.
- 5. Local Institutions of Outstanding Interest:**
- Although primarily excluded from main consideration unless they bring substantial value, these are local entities that have innovatively addressed a challenge related to water or ocean conservation, demonstrated a practice or model with high replication potential or achieved measurable positive impacts in their locality, inspiring larger-scale adoption.

3.3.2 Interests and needs of the private sector: energy, food, fishery, plastic reduction, blue tourism, restoration.

Needs:

1. **Clarity on regulations.**

Blue industry needs a clear understanding of government regulations and standards related to environmental protection and sustainability. Ambiguous or frequently changing regulations can create uncertainties, making it challenging for businesses to strategize and invest. Businesses, especially those with long-term investment horizons, rely on a stable regulatory environment to formulate their strategies. Clear regulations help industries identify potential risks, be they legal,

financial, or reputational. When regulatory expectations are transparent, businesses can preemptively address areas of non-compliance, thus mitigating penalties or negative public perceptions. Ambiguity in regulations can lead to inefficiencies. Companies might overinvest in certain areas out of an abundance of caution or underinvest due to misconceptions. Clear guidelines ensure that companies can optimize their operations to meet standards without unnecessary expenditures.

2. **Support for sustainable practices.**

Switching to sustainable models might require new technologies, training, or operational practices. The private sector needs guidance, resources, and expertise to further adopt these changes in Europe.

- Innovation and R&D: industries often innovate and develop new technologies or processes in response to regulatory challenges. A well-defined regulatory framework can serve as a catalyst for innovation, as businesses seek out solutions that not only comply with regulations but also provide a competitive advantage. In relation to the Mission, a vast growth of digitalization and the digital twin encompasses and stimulates the objectives set and thus a sustainable blue economy.
- Training programs: employees at all levels, from management to frontline workers, may require training to understand and adopt sustainable practices effectively. For example, shifts to smart shipping and AI require differently trained personnel.
- Clear guidelines and best practices: as industries navigate the realm of sustainability, having a repository of best practices or clear guidelines can be invaluable. These can serve as roadmaps, helping businesses identify the most effective and efficient ways to achieve sustainability goals.
- Networking opportunities: engaging with other businesses, industry groups, or consortiums that are also on the sustainability journey can be beneficial. Networking can facilitate the sharing of insights, challenges, and solutions, fostering a collaborative approach to sustainability.
- Regulatory flexibility: while regulations are necessary to ensure compliance, some flexibility in their application, especially during transition periods, can be helpful. This could be in the form of grace periods or phased implementation timelines, allowing businesses adequate time to align with new standards without compromising their operations. For a growing and sustainable society, adaptability is key.

3. **Financial incentives or support.**

Transitioning to sustainable business models can be capital intensive. Grants, tax breaks, subsidies, or low-interest loans can be pivotal in motivating businesses to take the sustainable route. Investors, shareholders, customers, and partners often seek reassurances that a business is compliant with all relevant environmental regulations. Clarity in this domain enhances trust and reinforces the reputation of businesses in the eyes of their stakeholders.

- Upfront costs: sustainable technologies, be it renewable energy infrastructure, wastewater treatment systems, or eco-friendly materials, often come with substantial upfront costs. While they promise long-term savings, the initial investment can be daunting for many businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Securing sustainability certifications, such as Fair Trade, Organic, or Energy Star, can be expensive. Yet, these certifications are crucial for market recognition and can provide a competitive edge.
- Risk mitigation: transitioning to new, sustainable models presents risks. There might be uncertainties regarding technology performance, market reception, or return on

investment. Financial cushions in the form of incentives can mitigate these risks, making the transition more palatable.

- Long-term viability: while the shift to sustainability is often seen through an environmental lens, it's also about ensuring long-term business viability. As resources become scarcer and regulations tighter, companies that have embraced sustainability early on, facilitated by financial support, will likely have a competitive advantage in the long run.
- Market penetration: sometimes, sustainable products or services are priced higher due to the costs involved in their eco-friendly production. Financial incentives can allow companies to price these offerings more competitively, aiding market penetration and consumer acceptance.
- Stimulating green investment: incentives can attract investors interested in green or sustainable ventures. An enterprise that benefits from tax breaks or subsidies can present itself as a more attractive investment opportunity for this growing cohort of environmentally conscious investors.

Interests:

1. Profitability and brand reputation.

At the core, businesses are driven by profits. They seek sustainable solutions that are not only environmentally sound but also economically viable. In the age of informed consumers, a company's environmental stance can significantly influence its brand image. Businesses are interested in being seen as responsible, environmentally conscious entities.

- Market access and recognition: companies that adopt sustainable practices often seek recognition for their efforts. Certifications, eco-labels, or access to special market segments can serve as incentives, validating their commitment and potentially offering a competitive advantage. Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) criteria are increasingly important for investors. Companies with strong sustainability practices often attract investment more easily and may enjoy better terms due to perceived lower risks associated with responsible business practices.
- Consumer expectations: today's consumers are more informed and conscientious. They often make purchasing decisions based on a company's environmental and ethical track record. Brands perceived as sustainable or eco-friendly can command loyalty and even premium pricing.
- Operational efficiency: sustainable business practices, such as waste reduction, energy efficiency, and circular supply chains, can lead to cost savings in the long run. These practices not only reduce environmental impact but also enhance profitability by cutting unnecessary expenses.
- Employee attraction and retention: a strong environmental stance can make a company more attractive to potential employees, especially the younger generation who often prioritize working for companies aligned with their values. Employee retention can also be higher in companies with strong sustainability initiatives, reducing costs related to turnover and recruitment.

2. Sustainability.

Sustainable practices ensure that industries have a steady supply of resources to tap into. For instance, the fishing industry depends on a healthy marine ecosystem to ensure a continuous and bountiful catch. Overfishing may provide short-term gains but can lead to resource depletion in the future, jeopardizing the industry's long-term survival. Adopting sustainable fishing practices

ensures that fish populations can regenerate, providing a continuous supply for the industry. Some flexibility of the sector to more innovative (offshore) food sectors could be key for collaboration and reach goals.

- Risk management and resilience: companies that integrate sustainability are often better equipped to anticipate and adapt to changes, be they regulatory, environmental, or market-driven. Such businesses are less vulnerable to resource shortages, fluctuating prices, and supply chain disruptions. For example, companies that rely on freshwater resources might invest in water conservation techniques.

3. **Market Demand.**

Consumer preferences are shifting towards sustainable and eco-friendly products. Whether it's sustainably caught fish, eco-tourism experiences, or biodegradable plastics, there's a growing market demand.

- Supply chain resilience: companies that adopt sustainable practices often engage with their suppliers to do the same. This can lead to a more resilient supply chain, as sustainable practices can buffer against disruptions like resource scarcity or regulatory changes.
- Long-term growth: while immediate profitability is a primary concern, businesses also look to the future. Companies that integrate sustainability into their core strategy are better positioned to adapt to future challenges, whether they be environmental, regulatory, or market-driven.
- Market differentiation: in crowded markets, a genuine commitment to sustainability can set a brand apart. This differentiation can be a significant competitive advantage, driving both sales and customer loyalty.

Table 6. Examples of engagement Strategies recommended for the private sector

Engagement Strategies (some examples):

- Regular dialogues: establish forums or platforms for regular communication between the Mission leaders, policymakers, and private sector representatives. This ensures that businesses are aligned with the Mission's goals and are aware of the support available to them.
- Training & workshops: organize training sessions and workshops to educate businesses on sustainable practices, technologies, and market opportunities.
- Recognition & awards: acknowledge and celebrate businesses that have made significant strides in sustainability. This not only encourages them but sets a benchmark for others in the industry.
- Collaborative projects: partner with businesses on pilot projects or initiatives. For example, collaborate with the plastics industry on waste reduction projects or with the tourism sector on promoting eco-tourism.
- Policy advocacy: advocate for policies that benefit businesses transitioning to sustainable models. This could include tax breaks, grants, or favourable regulations.
- Consumer awareness campaigns: drive campaigns to educate consumers about the benefits of choosing sustainable products or services, indirectly supporting businesses that have made the transition.

Blue Economic Sectors Key to Lighthouse Areas Development or influencing LH environment

'Lighthouse areas' refer to areas or sectors that are at the forefront in a particular domain. Economic sectors that are key for innovation are highlighted. These sectors drive change, set trends, and often pilot new strategies that others may follow, those are important when considering innovation and project generation needed helping towards reaching the Mission objectives set, primarily carbon neutrality and circularity, much aligned with biodiversity enhancement as well as pollution reduction to a well needed stop. This knowledge is mainly gained collaborating with experts in the blue economy sector, (eg. For Belgium: www.bluecluster.be).

1. Agriculture.

This sector is crucial as it deals with food production. However, its practices can significantly impact water quality and usage, with issues like runoff from pesticides and fertilizers and plastic affecting freshwater systems and beyond. Projects bringing innovative solutions to sector as well as the governmental structures leading it are welcomed.

2. Aquaculture.

Food production at sea is considered very important in the food transition (protein transition). Additionally, carbon and nitrogen capture at sea might play an important role in reaching the Mission objectives and valorising it. Some examples are given hereunder, wherein projects can be stimulated in reaching a better research and innovation as well as actual implementation.

- Use of sustainable and low-impact feed ingredients, such as alternative proteins like algae, insects, and plant-based sources, to reduce the carbon footprint and dependence on wild-caught fish for feed.
- Design and implement energy-efficient infrastructure and aquaculture systems, including closed-loop and recirculating systems, to minimize water and resource wastage.
- Transition to renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, and tidal power, for aquaculture operations to reduce reliance on fossil fuels.
- Stimulate seaweed and shellfish, as they can sequester carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, contributing to carbon neutrality, and develop monitoring for communication and developing possible credits to set up a business model.
- Develop systems for capturing and reusing excess nutrients, such as fish waste, for fertilization, contributing to circular resource use and reducing water pollution.
- Ensure that wastewater from aquaculture operations is treated effectively to prevent nutrient and contaminant discharge into the surrounding marine environment.
- Choose species that have a lower ecological impact, are well-suited to local conditions, and are not invasive. Implement measures to protect and enhance local biodiversity.
- Promote responsible health management practices that minimize the use of antibiotics and chemicals in aquaculture to reduce the environmental impact and the risk of antibiotic resistance.
- Implement circular economy principles within aquaculture, emphasizing the reuse and recycling of resources, such as water, waste, and nutrients.

3. (Blue) tourism.

As a major global industry, tourism can put pressure on local environments and water systems, from beach erosion to waste production in sensitive areas, as well as intensive product use and mass production. When the LH can evolve its activities in tourism towards sustainable blue tourism, including circularity in the sector, a better balance with less ocean pressure can be reached and the sector can evolve towards sustainable tourism activities with a reduced carbon

footprint. Some examples of how blue tourism can help and directions stakeholders can be engaged and which projects should be strengthened:

- Encourage the use of sustainable transportation methods for reaching coastal destinations, such as electric or hybrid boats, ferries, and ships, which emit fewer greenhouse gases compared to traditional vessels powered by fossil fuels.
- By implementing energy-efficient design and technologies in the construction and operation of hotels, resorts, and other tourism-related infrastructure along the coast, these facilities can reduce their energy consumption and carbon emissions. Use renewable energy sources, such as solar panels or wind turbines, to power their operations, reducing their reliance on carbon-intensive energy sources.
- Blue tourism activities like recreational boating and scuba diving can adopt responsible practices to minimize their environmental impact, such as following no-wake zones, anchoring in designated areas, and avoiding damage to sensitive marine ecosystems.
- Restaurants in coastal areas can support sustainability by serving locally sourced, responsibly harvested seafood and reducing food waste, thereby reducing the carbon footprint associated with food production and transportation.
- Promoting eco-friendly accommodations, such as eco-lodges and green hotels, can reduce the environmental impact of tourism by using energy-efficient appliances, low-flow water fixtures, and sustainable building materials.
- Raise awareness about the importance of marine conservation and sustainable practices. Tour operators can offer educational programs to tourists, encouraging them to support marine conservation efforts and become advocates for protecting the oceans.
- Implement carbon offset programs, where they invest in projects that capture or reduce carbon emissions, such as reforestation or renewable energy projects, to compensate for the emissions generated by their operations.
- Implement waste reduction and recycling programs to minimize their impact on the environment, including the proper disposal and recycling of waste generated by tourists.
- Collaborate with environmental organizations and seek certification to demonstrate commitment to sustainable practices and carbon neutrality.

4. (Blue) transport and transport infrastructures (smart and clean Ports).

Transportation, especially when considering ports, affects waterways and marine life. Ports can cause water pollution due to ship discharges, oil spills, and ballast water releases. Smart shipping and smart ports is an important evolution in port and shipping management and logistics, it contributes highly to both Mission objectives in the North and Baltic sea. Below some examples on which projects to stimulate making grateful use of the enablers of the Mission.

- Smart ports
 - use advanced technologies to optimize energy consumption. For example, they can implement intelligent lighting and HVAC systems that adjust based on real-time data, reducing energy waste.
 - can invest in renewable energy sources like wind turbines and solar panels to power port operations, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and lowering carbon emissions.
 - use data analytics and IoT (Internet of Things) sensors to optimize cargo handling, reducing idle times for ships at the port, which can lead to fuel savings and emissions reductions.
 - offer shore power infrastructure, allowing ships to plug into the electrical grid while at the dock, reducing the need for auxiliary engines and decreasing emissions.

- employ data analytics and digital platforms to better manage traffic and reduce congestion, which can lead to fewer emissions from waiting vessels.
- Smart shipping and ships
 - are equipped with emission monitoring systems to track and report emissions. They can also employ exhaust gas cleaning systems (scrubbers) to reduce sulfur emissions.
 - use advanced navigation systems and weather data to optimize routes and speeds, leading to fuel savings and reduced emissions. They may also employ innovative propulsion technologies like air lubrication systems and hull modifications to reduce drag.
 - may focus on circular economy principles by using recycled and sustainable materials for shipbuilding and adopting modular designs that facilitate easier component replacement, reducing waste and increasing ship longevity.
 - utilizes IoT and blockchain technologies to track containers, improving logistics, reducing idle times, and minimizing empty container repositioning, thereby saving energy and emissions.
 - use sensors and data analytics to predict equipment maintenance needs, reducing downtime and increasing the useful life of components and vessels, contributing to circularity.
 - may explore alternative fuels like LNG, hydrogen, and ammonia, or adopt electric and hybrid propulsion systems, which have lower carbon footprints compared to traditional marine fuels.
- Smart ports and shipping
 - implement efficient waste management systems to recycle and properly dispose of waste, reducing marine litter and promoting circularity.
 - promote data sharing and collaboration among stakeholders, including port authorities, shipping companies, and logistics providers, to optimize operations and reduce environmental impacts.

By leveraging these smart technologies and practices, both smart ports and smart shipping can help the maritime industry move closer to carbon neutrality and circularity, reducing environmental impacts and promoting sustainable operations.

5. Energy sector

The energy sector, whether it's hydroelectric dams or nuclear power plants, can have significant implications on water temperatures, flow, and aquatic life. To transform this into a positive project, for example, heat from a nuclear power plant on land can be used for another use at sea and not just released. The blue energy sector is transforming into sustainable energy and is a sector to focus on. Alternative blue energy forms are encouraged. Some examples are given to better reach the objectives:

- a. Develop and expand offshore wind farms, tidal energy installations, and wave energy facilities to generate clean, renewable energy, reducing the reliance on fossil fuels.
- b. Implement CCS technologies in offshore energy production to capture and store carbon emissions, helping to mitigate climate change.
- c. Invest in energy-efficient equipment and technologies to optimize energy production and storage, reducing waste and carbon emissions.
- d. Repurpose or retrofit existing offshore oil and gas infrastructure for renewable energy projects, reducing the need for new resource extraction.

- e. Develop floating platforms for offshore wind and solar installations, enabling energy production in deeper waters and increasing circularity.
- f. Promote the use of recycled and sustainable materials in the construction of offshore energy infrastructure, including turbine components, cables, and foundations.
- g. Plan for the responsible decommissioning of energy infrastructure, recycling materials whenever possible, and restoring the seabed to its natural state.
- h. Implement waste management practices for offshore energy operations, minimizing waste production and preventing marine litter.
- i. Implement measures to enhance local ecosystems around and on offshore energy installations, such as creating artificial reefs or marine protected areas. Nature Inclusive Design on Offshore infrastructure.
- j. Develop transmission infrastructure to export excess energy to shore, facilitating the integration of renewable energy into the broader grid system.
- k. Promote grid integration and smart grid technologies to efficiently manage and distribute offshore energy, reducing losses and enhancing sustainability.

Surely better data assembling and monitoring, as well as safety and security measures are key. In building infrastructure Environmental Impact Assessments are required, but also a strong involvement of SH and key experts can significantly contribute to the success of large marine infrastructure projects. In Belgium an example of development of an energy island at the Belgian coast side was presented. This has been designed by the co-creation and co-design processes. The co-creation process consists of “work benches”: clients and SH receive homework, and it’s a cycle where everybody co-creates and takes ownership eventually.

A group of small top experts were selected (not retributed) to work in the project, and ambitions and boundary conditions were set together. Then, for the setting of evaluation criteria, the process of joint fact finding started: the scope is to create a safe space where everything is questioned and should be proved, and a common language is used for all experts (i.e. drawings). Then sections are made (everything is asked to experts from different sections, e.g. biologist about biodiversity) and everything gets quantified and shapes are explored (of the island, of the floors etc.). Afterwards, construction methods are explored with clear and transparent zoom-ins. Then a continuous monitoring and evaluating process are set. For more info: www.orgpermod.com.

6. Waste management and ocean pollution.

Proper disposal and treatment of waste determine the quality of water in an area. Mismanagement can lead to polluted freshwater sources and seas. Some examples where innovation gaps are identified:

 - a. Plastic Recycling Programs: Businesses can initiate or support programs that recycle plastic waste, preventing it from entering the oceans. This can involve setting up collection points for plastic items and partnering with recycling facilities.
 - b. Circular Packaging: Implementing circular packaging solutions, such as using recycled materials and designing packaging that is easily recyclable, helps minimize the generation of single-use plastics.
 - c. Responsible Sourcing: Companies in the seafood industry can adopt sustainable and responsible sourcing practices. This includes supporting fisheries that use environmentally friendly methods and avoiding overfished species.
 - d. Reducing Bycatch: Implementing technologies and strategies to reduce bycatch, which is the unintentional capture of non-target species during fishing operations, contributes to a healthier marine ecosystem.

- e. Ocean Cleanup Technologies: Investing in or supporting the development of technologies designed to clean up existing ocean pollution, such as floating barriers and autonomous cleanup vessels, can be a significant contribution.
- f. Biodegradable Alternatives: Developing and promoting biodegradable alternatives to traditional materials can reduce the persistence of pollutants in marine environments.

7. Maripark

Maripark is a holistic approach of sustainable offshore industry (and connections, infrastructure, permits and regulations). The concept foresees in basic infrastructure, holistic approach of data assemblage, monitoring, easy and one stop permit application, combination of sea uses (energy, food, nature, tourism ...), an overall security system, cost reduction by combining (smart) transport for maintenance and so on. The actual design differs from the aim and the geographical parameters. Multi-use starts from two uses to several, and should be applied as a basic principle to start an offshore project (unless no additional use is possible) instead of single-use (compare with monocultural practices on land). The shared infrastructure, permit, maintenance, data and monitoring and safety and security system allow as for a higher efficiency and a least environmental impact – compared with the cumulative sum of impacts of single sectors. Surely to provide this scientifically, much extra research is needed on the concept, as well as several pilots should be installed.

The mentioned sectors not only play a role in the economy but also have a direct or indirect influence on freshwater and marine environments. This impact can be in terms of pollution, resource extraction, habitat disruption, or any other environmental aspect. Sustainable practices in these sectors are essential to preserve the health and balance of these ecosystems, as stressed above, turning the sector into sustainable they can help reaching carbon neutrality and circularity at sea, as well as inducing a higher biodiversity rate and end pollution. Eco-certifications, best practices, stimulating research and innovation and an enhanced and more holistic data, monitoring and publication system can improve lifting the SBE sector, as well as focused education and an enhanced regulation and subsidy system.

To conclude the non-exhaustive chapter on sustainable economy with a strong focus on blue economy, it is underlined that place at sea is scarce, and regulations, tenders and permits should be better aligned with each other. If this is done, a way to most efficiently use space at sea is to apply the principle of multi-use.

3.3.3 Interests and needs of the scientific research institutions

Needs:

1. Funding for Research.

As the worldwide focus shifts to repairing marine habitats, reducing pollution, and transitioning to a carbon neutral and circular blue economy, the role of scientific research institutes becomes increasingly important. These institutions are at the forefront of maritime innovation, understanding, and solution development. Their job frequently necessitates the use of specialised technology capable of measuring minute changes in marine health, mapping oceanic garbage, and even designing technologies that help to the development of a circular blue economy or cumulative impacts. Such new instruments, although necessary, come at a great cost. Furthermore, on-the-ground research necessitates activities in a wide range of terrains, from deep oceanic depths to crowded coastal zones, demanding not just transportation but also specialised gear and procedures. Once the data is acquired, laborious lab testing confirm its correctness,

necessitating the use of cutting-edge equipment and consumables. The multidisciplinary character of these difficulties necessitates the formation of teams of specialists from diverse fields, including biologists, ecologists, engineers, economics, and others.

Type of funding:

a. Public Funding:

- Government Grants: monetary resources allocated by governments for specific research themes or challenges.
- International Grants: funds that come from international bodies like the United Nations, World Bank, or regional bodies like the European Union.

b. Private Funding:

- Corporate R&D Investments: many corporations invest a percentage of their profits in research, particularly if it aligns with their business.
- Angel Investors and Venture Capitalists: individuals or groups that provide funding for promising research or innovations, usually expecting a return on their investment.

c. Mixed Funding:

- Co-funded Initiatives: collaborative funding models where multiple entities (both public and private) pool resources for a joint venture.

2. Open Channels of Communication with Policymakers (and beyond).

The 'BiodivERSA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook (2008)'¹¹, promotes cross cutting interdisciplinarity, integration of actors, delivery of academic excellence, improvement of societal impact, support for researchers conducting SHE and inclusivity in SHE, enhanced legitimacy societal relevance, visibility of research/EU investments, assurance that SHE keeps on going until the end of the projects.

Getting an agreement on complex issues is not straightforward: consider methods and available tools, communicate decisions and outcomes.

To ensure their research has practical applications and influences policies, scientists need direct lines of communication with those in positions of authority and decision-making. The nexus between science and policy is vital, especially when addressing intricate and pressing challenges like marine ecosystem restoration, pollution mitigation, and the evolution of a neutral and circular blue economy. Scientific research institutions, as repositories of knowledge and innovation, possess crucial insights that can shape effective and informed policies. However, this invaluable information can only be harnessed if there's a seamless flow of communication between researchers and policymakers.

Ensuring open channels allows for real-time updates, wherein emergent findings can be rapidly integrated into policy frameworks. It also fosters a collaborative spirit, enabling scientists to understand policy constraints and policymakers to grasp the nuances of scientific data. This synergy ensures that policies are not just aspirational but are grounded in empirical evidence, maximizing their efficacy.

Moreover, in the ever-evolving landscape of marine challenges, where new threats or opportunities can emerge, having a dynamic communication link ensures agility in policy formulation and implementation. For institutions, this means their hard work and discoveries have a tangible impact, driving real-world change.

3. Access to Sites and Data.

For accurate and thorough research, scientists need data, which might be held by governments, businesses, or other entities, an issue that has been raised above. The integrity and depth of

¹¹ <https://www.biodiversa.eu/research-funding/guides-capacity-building/stakeholder-engagement-handbook/>

scientific investigations often hinge on the ability to gather data directly from source environments and to tap into existing data reservoirs. Scientific research institutions often necessitate hands-on investigations in diverse marine and freshwater habitats, from the profound depths of open oceans to the dynamic ecosystems of estuaries and coastal regions. Access to these sites is pivotal, allowing researchers to gather first-hand samples, observe natural behaviours, and deploy monitoring equipment. Some of these sites, especially those with unique ecosystems or situated in strategic locations, might fall within territorial jurisdictions or protected zones, requiring permissions and collaborations. In addition, while primary data collection is crucial, a vast amount of valuable data already resides with various stakeholders – government agencies might hold monitoring and survey data; businesses, especially those in the blue-economy sector, might possess data on resource utilization and waste generation; international organizations might have consolidated datasets spanning multiple regions. For a holistic understanding and to avoid redundant efforts, research institutions need access to this plethora of existing data.

Interests:

1. Scientific discovery.

The intrinsic motivation of any scientific research institution is the unending pursuit of knowledge. In the vast and intricate world of marine sciences, there remain many mysteries yet to be unravelled. Research institutions are poised on the edge of groundbreaking discoveries about marine life. There is a constant quest to understand the complex interplay of marine organisms, their adaptation to changing environments, and their resilience or vulnerability to pollutants. Discovering new species, understanding migratory patterns affected by changing climates, or unveiling deep-sea secrets are just the tip of the iceberg. Moreover, as the global narrative shifts towards sustainability, there's an intensified drive to unearth innovative pollution removal techniques, comprehend microplastic interactions, or develop bio-remediation measures. These discoveries are not just academically exhilarating but have profound practical implications in restoring marine health. Lastly, the blue-economy, which envelopes sectors like fisheries, tourism, and marine biotechnology, holds immense potential for discoveries that align economic interests with environmental stewardship. Research institutions are deeply interested in innovations that can make industries more sustainable – be it through optimizing resource extraction, recycling marine waste, or pioneering biotechnologies.

Contribution to Knowledge and Innovation:

- a. Technological: leading-edge technologies that might offer solutions for cleaning polluted waters, restoring marine habitats, or efficient and sustainable fishing methods.
- b. Societal: innovations around societal structures, community involvement, and behaviour change, crucial for sustainable marine and water conservation practices.
- c. Organisational: new organizational structures or methods that lead to more effective conservation campaigns, policy implementation, or community outreach.

2. Conservation.

Conservation studies offer researchers a window into the intricate dynamics of ecosystems, species interactions, and natural processes. This aligns with the innate scientific curiosity to understand the natural world in its entirety. As global environmental challenges, such as climate change and biodiversity loss intensify, conservation becomes a topic of pressing significance. Research institutions recognize the urgency and adapt their research priorities to address these looming concerns.

Beyond the professional realm, there exists an ethical dimension. The knowledge and expertise vested within these institutions position them as stewards of the environment, prompting a moral

obligation to work towards its well-being. Conservation research often moves beyond mere observation, delving into solution-oriented studies. This actionable approach aligns with institutions' objectives to produce research that has a direct positive impact on society and the environment.

3. Evidence-Based Policymaking.

In the scientific community, there's a prevailing desire to ground policies and interventions in robust empirical evidence. Such an evidence-based approach not only promises more efficacious outcomes but also underscores the significance of scientific endeavours. Within the domain of conservation, empirical discoveries can significantly inform public policies, guidelines, and strategic conservation measures. By augmenting this reservoir of knowledge, research institutions wield the capacity to sway decision-making processes at the local, national, and international echelons.

d. Improving Regulatory Framework and Stakeholder Practices:

- Policy Recommendations: based on empirical research findings, these entities often provide insights that can shape or refine regulatory frameworks.
- Best Practices: through their R&D endeavours, they can identify, validate, and promote practices that yield the best conservation results.

e. - Regional or Trans-national R&D and Innovation Cooperation:

- Cross-border Collaborative Projects: these can tap into unique strengths, resources, and perspectives of different countries or regions.
- Shared Data and Resources: regional networks often facilitate the sharing of critical data, methodologies, and tools, leading to more consistent and impactful research outcomes.

4. Publication and recognition.

For many institutions, publishing findings in esteemed journals represents more than a mere dissemination of information. It serves as a hallmark of the rigor, quality, and relevance of their work. Gaining recognition in the expansive global scientific arena is pivotal for several reasons:

- a. Credibility: publishing in respected, peer-reviewed journals testifies to the validity and integrity of the research, reinforcing its acceptance and trustworthiness within and beyond the scientific community.
- b. Attracting talent: high-quality publications can serve as magnets for attracting budding scientists, experienced researchers, and potential collaborators. They position the institution as a hub for cutting-edge research, making it a desired destination for those seeking to engage in meaningful scientific efforts.
- c. Funding opportunities: recognition often opens doors to more substantial financial support. Funding bodies, governments, and philanthropic organizations are more inclined to invest in institutions that consistently produce reputable research, as this signals a higher likelihood of impactful returns on their investment.
- d. Influence and advocacy: published findings can influence policies, guide industry best practices, and inform public opinion. Being recognized for such contributions emphasizes the institution's role as a thought leader in the field.

Table 7. Engagement Strategies recommended for scientific research institutions

Engagement Strategies recommended

- Grants & Scholarships: establish funding programs specifically tailored for marine research. This could be in the form of research grants, scholarships, or fellowships.
- Regular Forums with Policymakers: organize meetings or conferences where scientists can present their findings directly to policymakers, ensuring that research informs decision-making.
- Data Sharing Platforms: create centralized platforms where data from different sources is aggregated, curated, and made available to research institutions.
- Collaborative research: facilitate collaborations between different research institutions, both nationally and internationally, to leverage collective expertise and resources.
- Recognition programs: institute awards or recognition programs to highlight significant scientific contributions in the field of marine conservation and restoration.
- Access permits: simplify and expedite the process for research institutions to obtain necessary permits for field studies, especially in protected or sensitive areas.

3.3.4 Interests and needs of the local communities

Needs:

1. Awareness and Education.

It's vital for local communities to understand the state of their surrounding marine environment, the challenges it faces, and the steps they can take to help. This understanding comes through effective awareness campaigns and education programs. Schools and community centres should incorporate marine conservation into their curricula. This could include field trips to local marine habitats, inviting experts for talks, and hands-on activities that teach conservation practices. Using various media, from posters to community radio, can help spread the message. These campaigns can highlight the importance of the marine ecosystem, the threats it faces, and what individuals can do to help.

- a. Cultural integration: in many communities, the ocean and water bodies play a significant cultural role. Integrating marine conservation with cultural practices can help in making the cause more relatable.
- b. Community involvement: engaging the community in projects such as beach clean-ups, ecosystem restoration, and mangrove planting can instil a sense of ownership and responsibility. Provide training and resources for communities to take the lead in conservation efforts. This could be in the form of workshops on sustainable fishing practices or training on how to set up and manage marine protected areas.
- c. Infrastructure and technology: proper waste disposal and recycling facilities can prevent pollutants from entering the marine environment. Equip communities with the tools and training to monitor their local marine environments. This could be as simple as providing smartphones for photo documentation or more advanced tools like water quality testing kits.
- d. Collaboration: encourage collaboration between local communities, NGOs, government agencies, and the private sector. Pooling resources and expertise can lead to more effective conservation efforts. Create platforms where communities can share their successes, challenges, and learnings with others. This can foster a sense of solidarity and provide valuable lessons.

2. Employment Opportunities.

Any restoration effort might alter the current state of employment (e.g., restricted fishing zones). In such cases, it's essential to provide alternative employment opportunities, preferably within the scope of the restoration mission. Local communities often depend on natural resources, such as fisheries, tourism or ecosystem services, for their livelihoods. When conservation or restoration efforts impact these resources – for instance, by declaring Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) or implementing Fisheries Restricted Areas (FRAs) – the immediate economic well-being of these communities can be jeopardized. Thus, providing alternative employment opportunities becomes not just a matter of economic sustenance, but also a way to ensure the success of conservation initiatives.

- a. Reduced reliance on exploitative practices: by offering alternative livelihoods, communities can move away from potentially harmful practices like overfishing, reducing pressure on vulnerable ecosystems.
- b. Strengthening conservation initiatives: when local communities are active stakeholders in conservation, benefitting directly from restoration activities, they're more likely to support and adhere to conservation guidelines. This community buy-in is crucial for the long-term success of any conservation effort.
- c. Skill development and diversification: introducing alternative employment can lead to skill development in the community. Training in areas like ecotourism, sustainable agriculture, or artisanal crafts can diversify the community's skill set, making them more resilient to future economic or environmental changes.
- d. Enhanced community well-being: secure employment is a fundamental pillar of community well-being. Stable incomes support better health, education, and overall quality of life. By ensuring that conservation efforts don't jeopardize local employment but instead bolster it, restoration missions can promote social equity and community welfare.
- e. Cultural preservation: often, sustainable employment opportunities can be designed around preserving and promoting local cultures and traditions. For instance, ecotourism initiatives can incorporate local storytelling, dance, or craft, ensuring that as the environment is restored, cultural traditions are also celebrated and maintained.
- f. Building a conservation ethic: involving local communities in restoration jobs, not only provides employment but also instills a deeper appreciation and understanding of the environment. Over time, this can cultivate a strong conservation ethic within the community.

3. Assurance of Well-being and Health.

Local communities are often the first to experience the direct consequences of environmental degradation, especially when it concerns water sources. Contaminated or polluted water bodies can lead to a range of health issues, from waterborne diseases to long-term chronic conditions due to exposure to toxins. As such, it is essential that restoration efforts also emphasize the health and well-being of these communities.

- a. Immediate health benefits: clean water is fundamental for various daily activities, from drinking and cooking to bathing. Ensuring that water bodies are free from pollutants reduces the risk of diseases like cholera, dysentery, and other waterborne illnesses. Additionally, the elimination of toxic chemicals and heavy metals can prevent long-term health complications, such as cancers or neurological disorders.
- b. Mental and emotional well-being: beyond the physical, there's a psychological dimension to clean environments. Water bodies often hold cultural, spiritual, or recreational significance for communities. Restoration can mean a return to traditional practices, rituals, or simply the joy of a rejuvenated natural space, promoting mental and emotional well-being.
- c. Strengthening trust in initiatives: by prioritizing the health and well-being of local communities, restoration missions can build trust. This trust is crucial for community buy-in, as people need to believe that these efforts are genuinely in their best interest and not just a distant bureaucratic objective.

- d. Economic health: healthy communities mean fewer medical expenses and days off due to illness, leading to greater economic productivity. Additionally, restored and clean water bodies can enhance tourism potential or boost fisheries, providing economic benefits to the community.
- e. Resilience against future threats: restoration projects that focus on health and well-being often take a holistic approach. This could mean not just cleaning up pollutants, but also creating buffer zones, mangrove plantations, or other natural barriers to future pollution sources or threats like sea-level rise, ensuring long-term community resilience.
- f. Community engagement and empowerment: when health is a focal point of restoration, community members, especially women and children who often bear the brunt of waterborne diseases, can become active participants in conservation. This engagement fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment, where the community doesn't just benefit from restoration but actively shapes it.

4. **Sustainable Resources.**

Local communities, particularly those nestled near aquatic ecosystems, often have intricate relationships with their surrounding environment. For many, the marine and freshwater resources are not just amenities; they are lifelines. Whether it's the fisherman who ventures out at dawn, the farmer who relies on river water for his crops, or the artisan whose craft is influenced by aquatic motifs, the pulse of these communities beats in rhythm with their waters.

- a. Economic incentives: many coastal communities rely on the ocean for their livelihood. Offering training and resources for sustainable fishing, aquaculture, or eco-tourism can provide both economic benefits and conservation outcomes. Local initiatives often require financial support. Setting up grant programs or providing low-interest loans can help communities kickstart or sustain their conservation efforts.
- b. Economic diversification: sustainable resource management might also involve introducing communities to alternative livelihoods that are both eco-friendly and economically viable. This could mean training them for ecotourism roles, aquaculture, or other sustainable marine-based professions.
- c. Adaptation and resilience: with the growing threats of climate change, sustainable resource management also implies adapting to new challenges. This might involve introducing communities to alternative, resilient species for cultivation in changing water conditions or techniques to protect against rising sea levels.
- d. Long-term food security: beyond immediate economic concerns, sustainable practices in resource management can have implications for food security. Over-depletion can lead to scarcity, and sustainable practices ensure that local communities have a steady food source.

5. **Representation.**

Local communities often possess a deep understanding of their environments based on generational knowledge. This knowledge, which may not be readily available in formal scientific literature, can offer invaluable insights into the sustainable management of resources, seasonal variations, and the intricacies of local ecosystems. Incorporating this traditional ecological knowledge can make policies more effective and tailored to the specific needs of the region. Representation ensures that policies are not just environmentally sound but also socially equitable. It can prevent the sidelining of local concerns in favour of broader national or international objectives, ensuring that the benefits of any interventions, such as economic gains or improved livelihoods, are shared fairly among local stakeholders.

Active representation of local communities can pre-empt potential conflicts. By giving communities a platform to voice their concerns, policymakers can address issues before they escalate. This can be particularly important in areas where there might be competing interests between conservation goals and community livelihoods.

- a. Community empowerment and participation: when local communities are involved in the policy-making process, they are more likely to take ownership of those policies. This fosters a sense of stewardship, where communities don't just follow rules but actively participate in their enforcement, understanding the reasons behind them. It's not about imposing rules from the top but about engaging the community in the decision-making process. This fosters a sense of ownership, where communities don't just follow sustainable practices but champion them.

Interests:

1. Livelihood.

Many coastal communities depend on oceans and waters for their livelihoods, through fishing, tourism, or other marine-based activities. They have a vested interest in ensuring the health and productivity of these ecosystems.

- a. Fishing and aquaculture: a substantial portion of coastal communities globally rely on fishing as their primary source of income. A healthy marine ecosystem ensures a steady and sustainable catch, which directly impacts their economic well-being. Additionally, aquaculture or fish farming ventures require clean water and balanced ecosystems to be profitable.
- b. Tourism: pristine beaches, vibrant coral reefs, and rich marine biodiversity are major attractions for tourists. Local communities often benefit from tourism-related activities such as guided tours, local craft sales, hospitality services, and more. A decline in marine health can lead to a drop in tourism, adversely affecting businesses and services that cater to tourists.
- c. Other marine-based activities: this includes industries such as seaweed farming, pearl farming, and salt extraction. The quality and quantity of produce from such activities are directly influenced by the health of marine ecosystems.

2. Cultural Preservation.

Oceans, rivers, and lakes often hold cultural and spiritual significance. Communities are interested in preserving not just the physical waters but the traditions, practices, and stories associated.

3. Sustainable Resources for Future Generations.

The idea of legacy is powerful. Communities are interested in ensuring that their future generations inherit a thriving, vibrant marine ecosystem. There is a profound desire among many communities to pass down a thriving and vibrant natural legacy to future generations. This entails not only maintaining but actively restoring and preserving marine ecosystems.

- a. Cultural and traditional significance: for many local communities, the ocean or nearby water bodies are not just sources of income but also hold significant cultural, spiritual, or ancestral value. Rituals, festivals, and traditions might revolve around these waters, making their health and sanctity a matter of emotional and cultural importance.
- b. Community identity and pride: for many coastal communities, the very identity of the community is intertwined with the ocean or the water body they live beside. A thriving marine environment can be a source of community pride and a symbol of their resilience and stewardship.

4. Health.

Clean water is a direct determinant of community health, affecting everything from the food they eat to the water they drink. Beyond commercial fishing, local communities often rely on oceans and freshwater sources for daily sustenance. A decline in fish populations or contamination of water sources can pose severe threats to local food security. Healthy marine ecosystems act as buffers against natural calamities such as tsunamis or storm surges. Mangroves, for example, play a crucial role in preventing shoreline erosion. Communities have an interest in maintaining these natural barriers to safeguard against environmental hazards.

Table 8. Engagement Strategies recommended for local communities

Engagement Strategies recommended:

- Community Workshops: organize workshops to educate and involve community members in restoration projects. This creates a sense of ownership and participation.
- Employment in Restoration Projects: engage community members in the restoration efforts, providing them with employment opportunities, whether it's in replanting mangroves, monitoring water quality, or guiding eco-tourism activities.
- Feedback Mechanisms: establish mechanisms for communities to provide feedback, voice concerns, or share local knowledge, ensuring their perspectives are considered in decision-making.
- Collaborative Resource Management: involve local communities in managing and monitoring marine resources, leveraging their on-ground presence and traditional knowledge.
- Health Monitoring: implement regular health monitoring camps or facilities to track and address any health concerns arising from water quality.
- Sustainable Practices Training: provide training on sustainable fishing, farming, or other practices to ensure that community actions align with the mission's objectives.

3.3.5 Interests and needs of the non-governmental strategies (NGOs) and environmental agencies

Needs:

1. Funding.

While passion and commitment drive many of these organizations, they require financial resources to undertake projects, campaigns, and research. This includes funds for operations, manpower, equipment, and awareness campaigns.

- a. Diverse funding sources: dependence on a single or few sources of funding can be precarious. NGOs often seek a diversified funding base, ranging from individual donors, grants, corporate sponsorships, to international aid, ensuring stability and sustainability in operations.
- b. Transparency and accountability: donors, both individual and institutional, are increasingly demanding transparency in the usage of funds. NGOs need mechanisms to report and showcase the impact generated from the funds received, emphasizing their credibility and effectiveness.

2. Collaborations and partnerships:

To maximize their impact, NGOs often seek collaborations with other entities, be they government bodies, businesses, or other NGOs. These partnerships can offer varied expertise, resources, and reach.

- a. Skill and knowledge exchange: collaborations can lead to an exchange of skills and knowledge. Partnering with academic institutions, for instance, can bring scientific expertise to the NGO, while a partnership with a grassroots organization might provide insights into local community dynamics.

- b. Joint initiatives: some environmental challenges are too vast for a single entity to tackle. Collaborative projects can pool resources, expertise, and manpower, ensuring larger-scale interventions with a higher likelihood of success.

3. Access to sites and data.

To monitor, study, and intervene effectively, these organizations need unhindered access to various marine sites, whether they're protected areas, pollution hotspots, or restoration zones. They also need access to data for informed decision-making and to measure impact.

- a. Research and monitoring: many NGOs engage in scientific research and monitoring activities. Unfettered access to marine sites ensures accurate data collection, essential for effective conservation strategies.
- b. Data sharing platforms: a centralized platform where different NGOs, researchers, and governmental bodies share data can streamline efforts, reduce redundancy, and provide a holistic picture of marine health and threats.
- c. Safety and equipment: accessing certain marine sites, especially those that are remote or in degraded conditions, might pose risks. NGOs require the right equipment, training, and safety protocols to ensure the well-being of their teams.

4. Advocacy support.

NGOs often champion causes that require policy changes or public support. They need platforms, allies, and tools to amplify their advocacy efforts.

- a. Media engagement: media can be a powerful ally in advocacy efforts. NGOs need to foster relationships with journalists, influencers, and media houses to gain coverage and bring attention to their causes.
- b. Public mobilization tools: from online petition platforms to tools for organizing public rallies or awareness campaigns, NGOs require resources to mobilize public support effectively.
- c. Legal and policy expertise: advocacy often involves navigating complex legal terrains and policy frameworks. NGOs benefit from having access to legal experts or consultants familiar with environmental laws and policies.

Interests:

1. Environmental conservation.

At the core of most NGOs in this realm is the objective of conserving the environment. This includes clean oceans, plastic-free waters, and thriving marine ecosystems. Many organizations are dedicated to preserving the diverse marine flora and fauna. They work to protect endangered species, habitats, and ensure the ecological balance of marine ecosystems.

- a. Marine Pollution Reduction: NGOs target sources of marine pollution, particularly plastics. Initiatives such as beach clean-up drives, public awareness campaigns about single-use plastics, and promoting biodegradable alternatives are some strategies employed.
- b. Marine Protected Areas (MPAs): NGOs push for the establishment of MPAs where human activities are regulated to protect marine life. They engage in research to identify ecologically significant areas that need protection.
- c. Sustainable fisheries: overfishing is a significant threat to marine biodiversity, for this reason NGOs work with fishing communities to find sustainable solutions as promote sustainable fishing methods, monitor fish stocks, and prevent illegal fishing.

2. Community upliftment.

A lot of NGOs intertwine environmental goals with community development. They work on projects that not only restore marine health but also uplift local communities, providing them with sustainable livelihoods and education.

- a. Sustainable livelihoods: NGOs often collaborate with fishing communities to shift towards sustainable fishing practices or alternative livelihoods, reducing the strain on marine resources.

- b. Education and awareness: offering educational programs in coastal communities about the importance of marine ecosystems helps instill a sense of responsibility. It also provides them with knowledge about sustainable practices.
- c. Eco-tourism: by promoting eco-tourism, NGOs not only facilitate conservation but also ensure that local communities benefit economically. It creates job opportunities and promotes a conservation ethic.
- d. Capacity building: training local communities in skills like mangrove plantation, aquaculture, and waste management ensures long-term benefits both for the environment and the people.

3. **Policy influence.**

To create lasting change, many NGOs and agencies aim to influence public policies. They work towards ensuring that government regulations, strategies, and actions align with environmental best practices.

- a. Marine conservation policies: NGOs advocate for stringent marine conservation laws, including those against ocean dumping, harmful fishing practices, and marine habitat destruction.
- b. Collaboration with International Bodies: NGOs often collaborate with international organizations like the UN to ensure the adoption and implementation of global standards and conventions related to marine conservation.
- c. Corporate accountability: NGOs lobby for stricter regulations on industries that pollute the oceans, such as the plastics industry, shipping, and oil and gas. They push for clean-up responsibilities and sustainable practices.
- d. Public mobilization for policy change: by organizing campaigns, workshops, and public demonstrations, NGOs can build public pressure, influencing policymakers to adopt pro-ocean policies.

Table 9. Engagement Strategies recommended for NGOs and environmental agencies

Engagement Strategies recommended:

- Grant programs: establish specific grant programs to support NGOs and agencies in their initiatives. These can be project-specific or general operational grants.
- Regular dialogues: organize forums or meetings where NGOs can discuss their findings, challenges, and requirements with policymakers, businesses, and other stakeholders.
- Shared platforms: create platforms where data, research findings, and best practices can be shared among NGOs, governments, and other stakeholders.
- Capacity building workshops: organize training sessions to enhance the capacities of these organizations, be it in the realm of research methodologies, community engagement, or advocacy tactics.
- Collaborative projects: initiate joint projects where governments, businesses, and NGOs work together, leveraging each entity's unique strengths.
- Public endorsement: publicly endorse and support the advocacy campaigns of NGOs, lending them additional credibility and reach.

3.3.6 Interests and needs of the general public

Needs

1. Education and awareness.

The general public requires access to clear and accurate information about the state of oceans and waters, the challenges they face, and how individuals can make a difference. This foundation of knowledge empowers them to take informed actions.

- a. Accessible information: the public requires easy-to-understand, concise, and up-to-date information about the state of oceans and waters. This includes multimedia resources, educational campaigns, workshops, and community outreach programs to cater to diverse learning styles and age groups.
- b. Local engagement: tailored information about the direct impacts and state of local marine and freshwater systems can make the message more relatable and immediate. Encouraging local schools, colleges, and community centres to incorporate marine conservation topics in their curriculum or activities can be beneficial.
- c. Behavioural change campaigns: the public needs guidance on actionable steps they can take in their daily lives to contribute to the mission. This might involve information on reducing plastic use, sustainable seafood consumption, and responsible tourism practices.

2. Transparency on initiatives.

People want to know how governments, businesses, and organizations are addressing the challenges. They seek transparent updates on the actions being taken, the funds being spent, and the progress achieved.

- a. Regular updates: governments, businesses, and organizations should provide regular updates on the progress of the Mission. This can be done through websites, annual reports, press releases, and public forums.
- b. Open Data Platforms: establishing platforms where data on marine health, initiatives' progress, and expenditure can be easily accessed and understood by the public. Interactive dashboards, maps, and infographics can make this information more engaging.
- c. Feedback mechanisms: the public should have avenues to voice their concerns, ask questions, and offer suggestions. This can be facilitated through town hall meetings, online forums, and feedback sections on official websites.
- d. Accountability measures: there should be independent bodies or watchdogs that can audit and verify the claims and progress reports made by governments, businesses, and organizations. This adds an extra layer of trust and credibility.

3. Assurance of environmental health.

The general public needs assurances that the water they swim in, the seafood they consume, and the marine environments they cherish are healthy and safe.

- a. Water quality monitoring: regular monitoring and public reporting of water quality, especially in popular swimming areas, fishing zones, and tourist spots, is essential. Accessible water quality indices can give the public a quick understanding of water health.
- b. Safe seafood guides: providing guidelines or certifications for seafood that is safe and sustainably sourced can help the public make informed choices. This includes information on fish populations, contamination levels, and sourcing practices.
- c. Health alerts: prompt public alerts on issues such as red tides, pollution spills, or other hazards ensure that people can take necessary precautions.
- d. Restoration efforts: visible efforts like beach clean-ups, mangrove plantations, and coral restoration not only improve environmental health but also provide tangible proof to the public of ongoing restoration efforts.

Interests:

1. Clean beaches.

A clean beach is not only aesthetically pleasing but also signifies a healthy marine environment. The public often associates their coastal experiences with the broader health of the ocean.

- a. Environmental indicators: a clean beach is often an indicator of a healthy marine ecosystem. The absence of litter, especially plastics, indicates reduced marine pollution which means less harm to marine animals and birds.
- b. Economic benefits: clean beaches attract tourists and boost local economies. Tourism related to marine environments is a significant source of revenue for many coastal regions.
- c. Cultural & spiritual significance: many communities have cultural or spiritual ties to the coast. Clean beaches maintain the integrity of these connections.

2. Healthy seafood.

Many people consume seafood as a regular part of their diet. They are interested in ensuring that the seafood they consume is free from pollutants and sourced sustainably.

- a. Health implications: seafood contaminated with pollutants, like mercury or microplastics, can have detrimental health effects when consumed by humans. Ensuring the health of seafood directly impacts public health.
- b. Economic aspects: the seafood industry is a significant economic sector in many countries. Ensuring the health and sustainability of seafood protects jobs and sustains businesses.
- c. Biodiversity: overfishing can lead to a loss of species diversity. Sustainable fishing ensures that marine ecosystems remain diverse and robust.

3. Recreational opportunities.

Oceans, rivers, and lakes offer myriad recreational activities, from swimming and boating to diving and fishing. A healthy marine ecosystem ensures that these activities remain available and enjoyable.

- a. Physical & mental health: marine recreational activities provide physical health benefits and can also serve as therapeutic outlets, reducing stress and promoting mental well-being.
- b. Community building: activities like beach outings, fishing trips, or boat races can foster community ties and create lasting memories.
- c. Economic relevance: recreational activities related to water bodies drive sales of related gear and equipment and boost businesses like rental services, lessons, and guided tours.

4. Well-being of future generations.

Many in the general public are motivated by the desire to leave behind a better world for their children and grandchildren. They're interested in long-term solutions that ensure future generations inherit vibrant oceans and waters.

- a. Legacy concerns: many people derive a sense of purpose from ensuring that the world they leave behind is in good condition for future generations. Protecting oceans and water bodies is a tangible way to contribute to this legacy.
- b. Educational opportunities: vibrant marine ecosystems offer educational experiences for younger generations, teaching them about biodiversity, ecology, and conservation.
- c. Long-term sustainability: a healthy marine ecosystem is essential for the planet's overall health. Oceans play a significant role in regulating climate, and their health has implications for global weather patterns, sea levels, and more.

Table 10. Engagement Strategies recommended for the general public

Engagement Strategies recommended:

- **Public awareness campaigns:** utilize various media platforms to launch educational campaigns. This could include documentaries, infographics, social media campaigns, and community workshops.
- **Feedback platforms:** establish platforms where the public can share feedback, ask questions, or voice concerns about the initiatives. This promotes transparency and fosters a sense of collective ownership.
- **Community involvement:** encourage community participation in clean-up drives, awareness walks, or citizen science projects. This hands-on involvement amplifies their connection to the cause.
- **Transparent reporting:** regularly publish reports on the progress of the mission, funds utilized, challenges faced, and milestones achieved.
- **Educational programs in schools:** incorporate marine conservation topics in school curriculums, nurturing a sense of responsibility from a young age.
- **Endorsement by local celebrities:** engage popular figures or celebrities to endorse and promote the mission, leveraging their influence to expand reach.

3.3.6.1 Toolbox to engage citizens and residents

As a product of prep4blue a toolbox to engage citizens and residents has been developed.

Public mobilisation and engagement are crucial elements of the European Commission’s Mission ‘Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030’. There is a wealth of approaches that facilitate this engagement including co-production of knowledge, citizen participation, activation and training, hackathons and citizen science initiatives.

With so many different approaches, it can be challenging to maintain an overview of methodologies, let alone choose a method to use among the many possibilities. To support this, PREP4BLUE partners from Nordland Research Institute and MaREI have developed a [Toolbox for Citizen Engagement](#)¹² (Figure 2) that maps the different ways in which participation can be facilitated and offers guidance on choosing an approach for different situations.

The toolbox is aimed at stakeholders including funding authorities, European projects under the Mission, individuals and organisations working on citizen engagement and the wider R&I community.

The toolbox includes a review of the underpinning theory and typology of citizen engagement approaches, an explanation of key terminology, a three-step framework for managing citizen engagement and, examples of tools and advice on aligning activities with the Mission.

The toolbox is an evolving document and will be added to as PREP4BLUE progresses, making use of feedback from Mission Ocean project participants and other users, until final delivery in 2025 (2022-

¹² Prep4Blue’s toolbox for citizen engagement: <https://prep4blue.eu/prep4blue-toolbox-for-citizen-engagement/>

2025 – Phase 1: development and piloting), when the toolbox ought to be available for deployment in the second phase of the Mission (2026-2030 – Phase 2: deployment and upscaling).

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

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Figure 2. Prep4Blue Toolbox on Engaging Citizens with the Mission

Source: Bjørkan et al. (2023) Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters: A toolbox of approaches. Milestone 6. Prep4Blue. (<https://prep4blue.eu/portfolio/toolbox-for-citizen-engagement/>).

3.3.7 Interests and needs of the philanthropists and investors

Needs:

1. Clear impact metrics.

Philanthropists and investors want to see measurable outcomes to gauge the impact of their contributions or investments. Well-defined key performance indicators (KPIs) and regular updates on progress are crucial. Impact metrics delineate quantifiable parameters and benchmarks established to evaluate the efficacy and outcomes of specific missions or interventions. These measurable criteria elucidate the magnitude of transformation and influence realized by philanthropic efforts. Within their stakeholder capacity, philanthropic institutions bear the responsibility of ascertaining that their inputs culminate in discernible, constructive alterations. Such metrics empower these entities to quantify and corroborate the resultant impact, championing an outcome-centric methodology. Additionally, they offer a foundational framework for refining tactical approaches, guaranteeing resource allocation to avenues promising optimal returns. Impact metrics pave the way for a methodical and unbiased assessment of philanthropic initiatives, embedding a fervour for purpose, accountability, and momentum, thereby actualizing philanthropic aspirations into tangible societal shifts.

2. Transparency.

In financial structures transparency is crucial because it builds donor trust, ensures ethical use of funds, and underscores the organization's commitment to the Mission. As donors become increasingly savvy and discerning about where their money goes, transparent financial practices become even more critical for philanthropic organizations seeking sustained support.

- a. **Budget breakdown.** A comprehensive financial breakdown grants prospective contributors an analytical perspective on the organization's efficacy and objectives. By elucidating each fiscal allocation, donors acquire a precise understanding of their contribution's deployment. It's advantageous to underscore the projected implications or outcomes corresponding to each budgeted segment. For instance, when funds are earmarked for scholastic resources, it's pertinent to indicate the projected reach, be it in terms of student beneficiaries or educational institutions impacted. Transparency regarding operational expenditures is paramount, reinforcing donor trust. Contributors find value in discerning whether their financial support addresses administrative necessities, such as remunerations, facility leasing, or other foundational costs. Furthermore, establishing a contingency fund or adaptive allocation is judicious to accommodate unexpected exigencies or emergent initiatives harmonizing with the organization's overarching vision.
 - b. **Financial auditing.** Consistent financial evaluations underscore an institution's dedication to fiscal responsibility, ensuring the judicious utilization of funds in concordance with the institution's overarching objectives. Collaborating with esteemed external audit entities bolsters the integrity of the audit process, with their autonomous evaluations guaranteeing unbiased scrutiny. The periodic dissemination of financial dossiers, whether quarterly, biannually, or annually, serves to apprise benefactors and stakeholders of the institution's fiscal status and undertakings. Facilitating the accessibility of these audit findings, possibly via the institution's digital platform or recurrent communiqués, empowers both prospective and established benefactors to peruse fiscal operations at their leisure. It's imperative for philanthropic entities to maintain a receptive stance to inquiries or critiques stemming from these financial disclosures, as such transparency cultivates a rapport anchored in trust with the patron community.
- 3. Efficient utilization of funds.**
- These stakeholders want assurances that their contributions or investments are being used judiciously. They seek lean operations, minimal overheads, and maximum on-ground impact.
- a. **Well-defined goals:** a thorough exegesis is necessitated, delineating precise endpoints and anticipated landmarks. This elucidation provides a methodological trajectory, grounded in empirical rigor, to navigate the pursuits.
 - b. **Scope and boundaries:** explicate definitions regarding the biogeographical zones, specific biotic assemblages, or human aggregates. This boundary-setting is essential for targeted interventions and facilitates the gauging of perturbations within the stipulated confines.

Interests:

1. Return on investment (for investors).

While philanthropists primarily focus on impact, investors look for both impact and a potential return on their investments. This could be in the form of profit shares, dividends, or appreciable equity, especially if they're backing for-profit social enterprises working towards ocean restoration.

2. Philanthropic impact.

Philanthropists are driven by the desire to make a positive change. They want to see tangible results, be it in the form of healthier marine ecosystems, reduced pollution levels, or empowered coastal communities. Donors want to know that their contributions are making a difference, and one way to persuade them is by presenting compelling, data-backed reasons.

Also ensuring a clear visualisation of data in graphs, charts, and infographics can make data more digestible and impactful. This is crucial when presenting to potential donors who may not be familiar with the intricacies of the cause. Moreover, providing a contextual analysis providing context beyond just raw numbers make results clearer to presented.

Case studies and examples of past interventions offer tangible proof of what's possible. They provide a narrative that potential donors can connect with and visualize.

- a. Detailed documentation. It's crucial to maintain thorough documentation of previous projects, including objectives, strategies employed, outcomes, and lessons learned.
- b. Human stories. While data is compelling, personal stories resonate on an emotional level. Sharing testimonials or narratives from beneficiaries or communities impacted by past interventions can be powerful.
- c. Impact measurement. Clearly demonstrate the change achieved through past interventions. This could be in the form of before-and-after comparisons, statistical improvements, or tangible on-ground changes.
- d. Replicability. Highlight how previous successes can be scaled or replicated in different contexts or regions. This assures potential donors that the model or approach has broader applicability.

3. **Legacy planning.**

Many philanthropists are motivated by the idea of leaving behind a legacy. Associating with a mission of this magnitude allows them to be remembered as champions of a significant environmental cause.

- a. Post-funding strategy.
With a clear post-funding strategy, projects can continue to thrive and benefit communities, ensuring that the initial philanthropic investment yields long-term dividends. It's a proactive approach to foreseeing and planning for the future needs of the Mission. Philanthropic entities, have a responsibility to ensure that the projects they fund do not become obsolete or dysfunctional once their direct involvement concludes. This means planning ahead, collaborating with local communities or organizations, and possibly identifying alternative funding sources or self-sustaining revenue models.
- b. Legacy initiatives.
These are hallmark projects or programs initiated by a philanthropic organization that continue to make an impact well beyond the funding period. They serve as enduring symbols of the philanthropy's commitment and vision. Legacy initiatives epitomize the philanthropy's lasting contribution to a cause or community. Philanthropies often seek to create such flagship projects as they not only amplify the organization's mission but also inspire other entities or future generations to engage in similar charitable activities. Legacy initiatives ensure that the benefits of the philanthropy's contribution are felt for generations to come. They often become benchmarks or models for subsequent philanthropic endeavours, elevating the standards and aspirations of charitable work in the given sector.

4. **Environmental and social change.**

In contemporary philanthropy, it's increasingly recognized that sustainable solutions are best derived from within the communities they aim to serve. As such, the role of philanthropic entities extends beyond merely providing financial resources. As stakeholders, they should actively involve and empower local communities to ensure that the initiatives are both meaningful and long-lasting.

- a. Local participation emphasizes the involvement of community members in every phase of an initiative, from conceptualization to implementation and evaluation. This ensures that the projects are tailored to the real needs of the community, leveraging local insights and knowledge. For philanthropic entities this means moving from a top-down approach to a more collaborative model. This shift fosters ownership among community members, ensuring that interventions are not only accepted but also valued and protected. Engaging local communities in the decision-making process leads to projects that are more relevant, culturally sensitive, and sustainable. With a sense of ownership, communities are more likely to contribute to, maintain, and further the initiative's goals.

- b. Capacity building refers to efforts aimed at strengthening the abilities, skills, and knowledge of individuals or groups within the community. This can include training, workshops, or providing resources that allow communities to drive their development and handle future challenges autonomously. Investing in capacity building means that the positive impact of an initiative can continue long after the initial philanthropic involvement has concluded. Empowered communities are better equipped to handle challenges, capitalize on opportunities, and ensure the longevity of initiatives. Through capacity building, the community transitions from being mere beneficiaries to active participants and drivers of change.

Table 11. Engagement Strategies recommended for philanthropists and investors

Engagement Strategies recommended:

- Regular reporting: provide detailed reports showcasing the impact metrics, financial utilization, challenges, and successes. This entails the systematic documentation and dissemination of progress, challenges, and results concerning philanthropic interventions. These documentations offer a concise overview of the current undertakings, the milestones attained, and sectors warranting further scrutiny. Periodic reportage reinforces transparency, an indispensable facet for philanthropic bodies in their stakeholder role. By disseminating these analyses, philanthropic institutions can foster profound interactions with a gamut of stakeholders, ranging from beneficiaries and collaborators to the broader populace. This practice not only serves to highlight achievements but also to identify potential enhancements and elicit constructive critiques. Consistent reporting fortifies trust within the philanthropic milieu. Keeping all stakeholders, be they donors, collaborators, or beneficiaries, consistently informed engenders a synergistic ambiance, ensuring congruent efforts and a unified commitment to the mission's fruition.
- Interactive platforms: create online platforms or dashboards where stakeholders can track real-time progress, financial metrics, and other relevant information.
- Engagement events: organize events, such as site visits, seminars, or workshops, where philanthropists and investors can engage directly with the mission's team, witness the impact firsthand, and provide feedback.
- Collaborative opportunities: offer opportunities for philanthropists and investors to collaborate on specific projects within the larger mission. This could be in the form of matching grants, co-investments, or partnerships on pilot projects.
- Recognition: effective acknowledgment of contributions, whether through the assignment of naming rights to structures, commemorative plaques, or inclusion in academic publications, serves to validate the impact of donors within the public sphere. Recognized philanthropic efforts, particularly when linked with successful projects or initiatives, bolster an organization's credibility. This enhanced credibility augments the likelihood of securing trust and collaboration from prospective donors or partners. Furthermore, public commendation can catalyze participation from other entities or individuals, motivating them to support the cause or contribute within their means.

3.3.8 Interests and needs of the media and influencers

Needs:

1. Access to Information.

For influencers and media professionals, access to information is paramount to their ability to inform, educate, and influence their audiences effectively. In order to have a real impact, they must comply with certain characteristics such as:

- a. Timeliness: in the fast-paced digital age, being the first to report or comment on an event or development can make a significant difference and have a real-time access to information is crucial.
- b. Accuracy: have access to accurate and verifiable information is crucial to maintain trustworthiness in the eyes of their audience.
- c. Comprehensiveness: to provide a holistic perspective on any topic, influencers and media professionals seek comprehensive data, encompassing all facets of an issue.
- d. Relevance: information that aligns with current events, trending topics, or audience interests is essential. Irrelevant data can lead to disengagement.
- e. Clarity: complex topics need to be broken down into understandable segments for a diverse audience.
- f. Sources: knowing the origin of the information, whether from experts, firsthand witnesses, or official releases, is crucial for verification and credibility purposes.
- g. Multimedia Elements: in the digital age, text often goes hand-in-hand with visuals. Access to high-quality images, videos, infographics, or audio can enhance storytelling and engagement.

2. Stories and updates.

Narratives rooted in real-world experiences provide an anthropological perspective to the expansive challenges of marine degradation. By elucidating the direct implications on individuals or communities, media entities and influencers transform abstract or geographically remote concerns into tangible and proximate matters for their constituents. Such firsthand accounts can elicit potent emotional responses, ranging from empathetic resonance to pronounced indignation. These affective reactions have the potential to catalyse proactive behaviour, from endorsing marine conservation initiatives to modifying individual consumption patterns or championing legislative reforms. Given the multifaceted nature of marine-related challenges, there exists a plethora of narratives—be it from fishermen observing diminishing yields, or coastal settlements grappling with the ramifications of sea-level rise. Disseminating a spectrum of these narratives ensures comprehensive representation of the marine challenge and tailors the discourse to diverse audience segments.

3. Collaboration for awareness campaigns.

In the realm of outreach and communication, collaborations are fundamental for media professionals and influencers, amplifying the potency of their narratives. Engaging in synergistic endeavours with esteemed entities, such as governmental bodies, non-governmental organizations, or academic institutions, not only enhances credibility but also cultivates a comprehensive understanding of the pertinent issue. By aligning with these reputable entities, media and influencers acquire an emblem of authenticity, indispensable when elucidating intricate or potentially polemical topics to the populace. Such synchronized engagements ensure consistent messaging across diverse media, bolstering clarity and mitigating potential interpretative discrepancies. The confluence of resources, whether fiscal, innovative, or operational, in these collaborative ventures often yields content of superior calibre, extensive dissemination, and a broadened audience spectrum. The multifaceted nature of collaboration means each participant introduces a unique audience, extending the message's reach from local

communities to a global scale. This collaborative architecture inherently promotes reciprocal communication, empowering media and influencers to refine their content based on feedback, queries, or concerns voiced by their partner's audiences.

Interests:

1. Viewer engagement.

Media outlets and influencers are constantly seeking content that engages their viewers, readers, or followers. Environmental topics, particularly those with a sense of urgency like ocean restoration, can capture attention.

- a. Relevance and timeliness: environmental topics, especially those related to imminent challenges like ocean degradation, resonate with global audiences. These issues, being of global concern, offer media and influencers the opportunity to present content that is universally relevant, timely, and impactful.
- b. Visual appeal: the ocean and marine life provide a wealth of visually stunning content, from colourful coral reefs to majestic marine animals. Such imagery can be highly engaging, leading to increased viewer interactions, shares, and discussions.

2. Education.

Many influencers and media professionals take pride in educating their audience about pressing issues. They appreciate content that is not only engaging but also informative.

- a. Raising awareness: many influencers and media entities value their role in enlightening their audiences about significant global challenges. They seek to present facts, statistics, and expert opinions that can foster a well-informed viewer base.
- b. Driving change: by educating their followers about sustainable practices, threats to marine ecosystems, or ways to contribute to restoration efforts, media and influencers can drive tangible changes in behaviours, attitudes, and even policies.

3. Storytelling.

The media thrives on storytelling. Chronicles of the ocean's degradation, the species affected, communities at risk, and the heroes leading the charge for change are all captivating tales waiting to be told.

- a. Human interest stories: the impacts of ocean degradation on local communities, fishermen, or even marine researchers can provide compelling human-interest stories. These narratives bring abstract issues closer to home, making them relatable and emotive.
- b. Narratives of hope and innovation: stories showcasing innovative solutions, restoration success stories, or profiles of individuals and organizations making a difference can inspire and uplift audiences. Such narratives can balance the often-dire news about environmental challenges, offering a ray of hope.

4. Reputation.

Associating with a noble cause like ocean restoration can enhance an influencer's or media outlet's reputation. It showcases them as responsible, aware, and committed to the betterment of the planet.

- a. Positioning as thought leaders: by consistently covering pressing environmental topics, media outlets and influencers can position themselves as thought leaders in the field. This can attract a dedicated, passionate audience segment keen on environmental matters.
- b. Building trust: associating with meaningful causes like ocean restoration demonstrates a sense of responsibility and commitment. Audiences often place higher trust in entities that show genuine concern for global challenges.
- c. Partnerships and collaborations: having a reputation for covering environmental topics can lead to collaborations with NGOs, environmentalists, researchers, and even governmental

bodies. Such collaborations can further enhance credibility and provide access to exclusive content or expert insights.

Table 12. Engagement Strategies recommended for media and influencers

Engagement Strategies recommended:

- **Regular briefings:** hosting periodic press briefings or webinars serves as a foundational strategy to keep the media and influencers abreast of ongoing activities and developments. Not only do these sessions provide updates about the mission's progress, but they also offer a platform for open dialogue, where questions can be addressed, thus ensuring that the message relayed to the public is accurate and comprehensive.
- **Content packages:** in an era dominated by digital consumption, readily available content is gold. By curating content packages, treasure troves of ready-to-use materials are made available/are offered. This can include captivating stories that highlight the human or ecological aspect of the mission, pertinent statistics that underscore the urgency or success of the efforts, and visuals—photos, infographics, or video clips—that add a layer of engagement and tangibility. Such packages can be invaluable for media houses running tight on resources or influencers looking for credible content to share.
- **Exclusive invites:** offering firsthand experiences, like guided tours of restoration sites, can be transformative. It shifts the narrative from abstract to personal. For an influencer or journalist, witnessing the on-ground efforts, challenges, and successes can lead to deeper, more heartfelt communication about the mission. Such immersive experiences often translate to authentic stories and testimonials that resonate more with audiences.
- **Recognition:** just as businesses value customer loyalty, it's pivotal to acknowledge the consistent support from media and influencers. Recognizing their contributions—whether it's a news outlet that has provided extensive coverage or an influencer who has rallied significant public support—fosters a sense of partnership. Awards, certificates, or even simple public shout-outs can motivate them to stay invested and continue their advocacy for the mission.
- **Feedback loops:** engagement is a two-way street. While it's essential to provide information and resources, it's equally crucial to listen. By setting up channels for feedback, be it through regular meetings, surveys, or informal chats, you can glean insights into their needs, expectations, and suggestions. Such feedback can illuminate areas for improvement, identify gaps in communication, or even offer innovative ideas to amplify the mission's reach and impact.

4 Smart specialisation strategies

Smart specialisation strategies are a useful tool to support transition towards a sustainable blue economy by creating the necessary blue economy oriented innovation ecosystems in Member States and regions by promoting the exchange of know-how/lesson learned, facilitating the creation of a blue economy community of S3 stakeholders and supporting the development of future blue economy based interregional innovation partnerships. In addition, Smart Specialisation cooperation can reinforce regional cooperation in the framework of the EU sea-basins and macro-regional strategies

as well as develop complementarities and synergies with the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF).

From an economic perspective, there are two important elements (Source JRC, EC Presentation of the reflection around the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process): first information gaps in innovation and industrial policies and secondly address coordination failures and encourage knowledge spill-overs across the private sector (stimulating more cooperation across private sector). These elements stand from research studies. What is already well achieved is a strengthened involvement of stakeholders in both innovation policies and regional/national funding strategies (ESIF), making innovation policies more evidence based, positive effects in terms of policy learning and prioritization and improving communication and coordination amongst a broader array of actors. Further improvement is needed for the quality of the process which is very different according to policy capacities, institutions, local cultures and historical experiences with innovation policies, scant participation of civil society and small enterprises, less participation of some actors, lack of skills and resources sometimes prevented actors from meaningful contribution, issues in vertical and horizontal coordination and EDP led in some instance to too many priorities. This is an ongoing process. A more holistic approach towards R&I funding is key. The role of the region in innovative process is being a facilitator between research, public policy and business and rely on the regional strategic priorities to create a leverage effect.

4.1 Open discovery process (ODP)

¹³A core objective of the ODP is the establishment of **Challenge-Oriented Innovation paRtnerships (CHOIRs)**.

- Multi-stakeholder and multi-level (government) partnerships.
- Linked to concrete territorial challenges.
- Challenge-oriented or mission-oriented.
- Emphasis on agreement, co-creation and co-ownership.

Challenges defined in terms of collectively determined and broadly understood goals. A combination of shared understanding of goals and autonomy about their implementation allow broad stakeholder coalitions to explore multiple pathways, maximizing the chances to achieve the goal. The key elements are set:

CHOIRs Key elements:

- (1) Goals: Agreeing on common goals is a key first step. To ensure alignment with European goals, Territorial goals will have to be seen through the lens of the twin green and digital transition;
- (2) Partners: Partly a function of the goal and vice versa. The relevant parts of public and private stakeholders will vary according to the goal;
- (3) Partnership teams: Executive bodies consisting of stakeholders who engage with representatives of different sets of stakeholders, according to the goal, working under a whole-of-society approach;
- (4) Open agendas: Partnership teams co-develop a collective open and dynamically adjusted agenda describing their proposed path for achieving the goal. Stakeholders open their individual agendas in relation to the goal, permitting synergies in the policy mix and sequencing of actions;

¹³ Source, workshop stakeholders2CoDesign and <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/w/what-lessons-are-there-for-open-discovery-process-odp-from-the-entrepreneurial-discovery-process-edp-experience>

- (5) Partnership hubs: Composed solely of public officials from various parts of government. Hubs provide the interfaces with the parts of government that can help accomplish the goals.

An example of the smart specialization strategy of the region of Occitanië¹⁴:

La Région Occitanie Pyrénées – Méditerranée: the region consists out of 220 km of coasts, with the following threats: erosion of the sideline, marine submersion, marine pollution, aging infrastructures, demographic and urban pressure, economic activities to strengthen and develop. A challenge is to be able to reformulate the littoral and maritime territory, to give it a new dimension.

The role of the region in innovative process is being a facilitator between research, public policy and business and rely on the regional strategic priorities to create a leverage effect as mentioned above.

In 2022, a study measure economic dynamics of region helping with the identification of several activities composing the Blue Economy and helping the regional economical level to find new financial solutions and be a significant leverage and encourage innovation and propose new solutions recognizing Occitane as a strategic leader.

The following tools where used

- For the Strategic level
 - Smart Specialisation Strategy: this strategy was elaborated in 2020 for 7 years (2021-2027) and is part of regional Green Pact for a sustainable economy within 5 topics: Floating offshore wind, Smart & Green boats, Smart & green Harbours, Coastal ecological engineering, Bioresources and blue biotechnologies. Regular working groups were held with all willing stakeholders on the 5 topics, with priorities based on expressed needs.
 - Regional scheme for economic development, innovation and internationalization
- For the Civil society
 - Parliament of the Sea: to bring the strategy into line with civil society stakeholders and their needs: unites and represents the maritime community, bringing forward projects and new ideas, innovations, best practices, organize dialogue, debate and mutual understanding. Also carries out national and European lobbying. The parliament applies 3 decision levels: a forum (1573 members), an assembly made up of 4 colleges (212 members) and an executive office (20 members).
- For the businesses
 - Avenir littoral call to attract companies with innovation projects in several themes (2 or 3 themes by edition of the call)
 - Sectors contracts: fishing, boating, aquaculture

¹⁴ Best practice of stakeholder engagement in the elaboration of regional smart specialization strategies - Entrepreneurial Discovery Process in Occitanie region (Workshop Stakeholder2codesign, Nicolas Dourlens, Occitanië):

5 Understand Stakeholders rights and duties

Stakeholders encompass individuals, groups, and organizations with a vested interest in a given project. This vested interest typically pertains to financial or strategic aspects, though it may also encompass ethical considerations, which we mention but further not investigate in this deliverable. Examining specific project-related stakeholder processes reveals a notable absence of a well-defined framework for delineating the complete stakeholder cohort. In other words, we currently lack precise criteria to determine the legitimacy of an interest's inclusion within the stakeholder group. Strikingly, there is no established legal context for a priori assessment. The evaluation of whether a claim is legitimate usually occurs within a legal framework following legal complaints against specific projects, such as the procedures overseen by the relevant authorities among Europe such as a Council of State. It is understandable that the development of legal frameworks has yet to be undertaken. Establishing such a legal framework is a multifaceted and intricate endeavor due to the diversity of stakeholder groups that can exist in different contexts, such as corporate governance or environmental regulations. Consequently, creating universally applicable legally binding criteria presents a significant challenge.

Nonetheless, it is evident that the legal framework should duly acknowledge the significance of the project context. One potential approach is to devise a specific methodology for the initial identification of potential stakeholders. This initial identification can serve as a foundation upon which a set of criteria can be applied to assess their legitimate interests. A possible avenue to explore is the formulation of legally binding definitions for each stakeholder category. These definitions should encompass both the conditions under which an entity qualifies as a stakeholder and outline their associated rights and responsibilities.

These rights and obligations encompass entitlements to access information, engage in decision-making processes, obtain background information and alternatives, and establish mechanisms for accountability. The legal framework can additionally outline reporting obligations and ensure transparency, addressing current deficiencies in this regard.

The enactment of legislation that formally codifies this legal framework will ensure its alignment with existing laws. Granting stakeholders a legal right to participate in the stakeholder process in a legitimate manner is likely to prove invaluable in the coming years.

6 Collaborative governance

Collaborative governance is a strategic approach in public policy formation and execution that constructively involves individuals from the public sector, private sector, and civil society. This method is designed to unite a varied group of stakeholders, encompassing government bodies, local communities, industry players, NGOs, and academic institutions, to participate in a unified decision-making and policy implementation process. By embracing the diversity of viewpoints, interests, and expertise, and acknowledging the interwoven nature of social, economic, and ecological systems, collaborative governance strives to forge more credible, well-informed, and enduring outcomes, especially within the realm of marine policy. As the challenges facing the world's oceans become increasingly global and complex, such as overfishing, pollution, and climate change effects, collaborative approaches become even more crucial for effective marine governance.

Implementing collaborative governance is often challenging due to differing objectives, varying levels of trust, and power imbalances among stakeholders. However, when successfully applied, it can lead to more resilient marine ecosystems, sustainable economic opportunities, and stronger communities.

Collaborative governance is not just a framework for inclusive decision-making; it's a multifaceted approach that incorporates various strategies essential for addressing complex and interconnected challenges. These strategies include Integrated Management, Adaptive Management, Conflict Resolution, Co-Management, Policy Development and Implementation, Capacity Building and Education. Each plays a crucial role in ensuring that governance is dynamic, responsive, and effective. These components are interlinked, each reinforcing the other within the collaborative governance model. They work in concert to create a governance system that is not only participatory and inclusive but also robust and equipped to tackle the multifaceted nature of marine policy challenges.

For the ocean, this is complicated because it should involve international, national and local stakeholders for efficient ocean governance. The system as it is now is complex and several platforms and governmental structures exist within the EU, that however often work together. A short, non-exhaustive, list is included in the table below (Table 13).

Table 13. A shortlist on relevant EU agencies and transboundary/regional agencies

EU policies and agencies, governance	Objective
Common Fisheries Policy (CFP)	regulating fisheries in European waters.
European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)	EU agency responsible for improving maritime safety, preventing and combating pollution from ships, and monitoring the implementation of EU maritime legislation.
European Environment Agency (EEA)	provides information on Europe's environment, including coastal and marine ecosystems, and contributes to policies aimed at protecting the marine environment.
European Space Agency (ESA)	uses satellite technology to monitor and manage various aspects of the oceans, such as sea level rise, ocean circulation, and environmental changes.
North-East Atlantic Fisheries Organization (NEAFC)	intergovernmental organization that manages fisheries in the North-East Atlantic, including many areas off the coasts of European countries.

OSPAR Commission	regional intergovernmental organization that focuses on the protection of the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic, including the North Sea and the Atlantic coast of Europe.
Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (HELCOM)	intergovernmental organization working to protect the marine environment of the Baltic Sea region, which includes several European countries.
International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES)	ICES is a scientific organization that provides advice on the sustainable management of marine resources in the North Atlantic, including areas off the coast of Europe.
European Marine Board (EMB)	EMB is a network of marine research organizations in Europe, which promotes marine science and provides advice to policymakers on various marine issues.
European Space Agency (ESA)	ESA uses satellite technology to monitor and manage various aspects of the oceans, such as sea level rise, ocean circulation, and environmental changes.

These organizations and governmental structures (Table 13) collaborate to address various ocean-related challenges, such as overfishing, marine pollution, climate change impacts, and the conservation of marine biodiversity. They help coordinate policies, research, and actions to protect and sustainably manage the European marine environment.

The project moves towards best practice knowledge management system, supported by AI digital tools and to ensure identification and management of innovative solutions. An enabling environment is being created from a regulatory and economic perspective, this should pave the way for public and private investment in future initiatives aligned with the objectives as well as an inspiring communication strategy.

6.1 Integrated Management

The current state of marine governance is fragmented, which hinders its effectiveness. To address this a novel multi-level governance approach that is more integrated and agile, capable of dealing with the complex developments occurring at sea, along shores, and on land is required. Marine ecosystems do not conform to political boundaries, so collaborative governance often requires an integrated approach that considers entire ecosystems. This may include cross-jurisdictional coordination and the development of regional marine policies. An integrated management in marine polices refers to a coordinated approach to managing marine resources and spaces that takes into account the complex interrelationships between different governances, ecosystems and human activities. This holistic method is essential for the sustainable use of marine resources and the health of marine ecosystems. Integrated management acknowledges that individual uses of the ocean and coasts, such as fishing, shipping, and recreation, do not occur in isolation; they interact with and affect each other and the environment. To this end, specific Integrated Management approaches within marine governance are:

- **Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM)**: is a holistic and integrated approach to managing the environment that seeks to ensure the long-term health and sustainability of ecosystems while allowing for the sustainable use of their goods and services. It is increasingly viewed as

essential for addressing complex environmental challenges, such as climate change, habitat destruction and biodiversity loss. Marine policies often adopt an EBM approach that considers the entire ecosystem, including human impacts and the cumulative impacts of different activities on marine ecosystem to develop a sustainable use of ocean resources.

- Marine Spatial Planning (MSP): is a process that guides where and when human activities occur in marine spaces. It's a practical way to create and establish a more rational organization of the use of marine space and the interactions between its uses, aiming to balance demands for development with the need to protect the environment, and to achieve social and economic objectives in an open and planned way. European Union's Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (2014/89/EU) established a framework for maritime spatial planning and integrated coastal management. Member states are required to establish maritime spatial plans by 2021.
- Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM): is a dynamic, multidisciplinary, and iterative process to promote sustainable management of coastal zones. It covers the full cycle of information collection, planning (in its broadest sense), decision making management, and monitoring of implementation. ICZM takes into account the fragility of coastal ecosystems and landscapes, the diversity of activities and uses, their interactions, the maritime tradition, and the particularities of coastal zone economies. The European Union's ICZM Recommendation (2002/413/EC) provided a common European framework for the implementation of ICZM in EU member states while, the Protocol on Integrated Coastal Zone Management in the Mediterranean (the ICZM Protocol adopted in 2008 as part of the Barcelona Convention, it is the first legally binding regional agreement specifically aimed at ICZM.

Stakeholder engagement is crucial in the integrated management of marine ecosystems, as it ensures that the interests and knowledge of all parties are considered in the decision-making process. The inclusion of stakeholders—such as local communities, industry representatives, conservationists, and scientific experts—enables a more comprehensive understanding of the ecosystem and the impacts of human activities. It also fosters collaboration and buy-in from those who will be affected by or can affect marine policies. When stakeholders are engaged in Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM), Marine Spatial Planning (MSP), and Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM), their diverse perspectives can contribute to more effective and equitable governance of marine resources. Their participation can help identify and prioritize objectives, co-create management strategies, and monitor the outcomes, leading to policies that are both sustainable and acceptable to the majority. This inclusive approach is more likely to result in resilient marine ecosystems and sustainable economic and social benefits.

6.1.1 Project examples

NAPSEA: in MOE database, not in SHEM tool, SHEM unknown

Funded by: Horizon Europe

Objective: This project focuses on the connections between land, water, delta, estuary, coast, nearshore, and ocean ecosystems, promoting a holistic approach to socio-economic development and environmental management. The project's geographical scope includes the Wadden Sea catchment, with case studies for the Rhine, Elbe, and Hunze catchments and the Wadden Sea itself.

CORDIS link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060418>

Respon-SEA-ble:

Funded by: H2020

Objective: This project specifically developed communication tools for mutual learning, indicating active engagement with various stakeholders to emphasize the role of civil society in ecosystem management.

Stakeholder engagement: interactive workshop – think tank

CORDIS link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/652643>

SEAPLANSPACE: not in CORDIS, not in MOE database

Objective: The project developed marine spatial planning instruments for sustainable marine governance, including SeaPlanSpace manuals for organizing knowledge, a portal on MSP, and a network for the Baltic Sea.

Land-Sea-Act: not in CORDIS, not in MOE database

Objective: This project guided authorities and stakeholders to improve cooperation, knowledge exchange, raise awareness, and balance development with coastal community interests, improving coastal governance.

HERMES: not in CORDIS, not in MOE database

Funded by: Interreg cooperation programme “Balkan-Mediterranean 2014-2020”

Objective: Developed a harmonized framework to mitigate coastal erosion by promoting an Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) protocol implementation.

Marine SABRES:

Funded by: Horizon Europe

Objective: Supports socio-ecological systems to aid ecosystem-based management in three case studies.

Stakeholder engagement: co-design

CORDIS link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058956>

COMMON: not in CORDIS, not in MOE database

Funded by: EU, ENI CBCMED, Sardegna Region

Objective: Achievements include the development of a coastal management and monitoring network for tackling marine litter in the Mediterranean Sea through an ICT platform for sharing methodologies and data on marine litter.

6.2 Adaptive Management

Adaptive management within the framework of joint governance in marine policy is a cyclical, knowledge-driven method that recognizes the intricacy and unpredictability of marine ecosystems. It emphasizes adaptability, modifying regulations and methodologies based on fresh scientific insights and shifts in environmental, social, or economic contexts. This strategy employs scientific surveillance and feedback loops to guide continuous policy refinement. Incorporating stakeholder engagement is crucial to this process, as it ensures that the perspectives and expertise of those directly affected by marine policies are considered. This inclusivity enriches the decision-making process, leading to better outcomes for marine ecosystems, more sustainable resource utilization, and enhanced conditions for

communities reliant on these resources. By integrating effective collaborative governance with stakeholder participation, adaptive management can significantly boost marine conservation efforts. Adaptive management requires:

- **Flexibility:** policies are implemented with the understanding that management strategies will evolve as managers learn from outcomes. Regular monitoring of the marine environment and human activities provides data that inform management decisions. Managers may test different approaches in controlled, small-scale experiments to learn what works before wider application. Policies and practices are designed to be adjusted rather than static, allowing for swift changes, when necessary, adapted in response to new scientific information or changes in the ecosystem. Stakeholder engagement is pivotal in this process, as it ensures that the diverse experiences and knowledge of those with a vested interest in marine policies are integrated into the learning cycle, thereby enhancing the responsiveness and relevance of management strategies.
- **Monitoring and evaluation:** clear, measurable objectives are established for marine resource use and conservation. Strategies are developed to meet objectives with the understanding that these strategies will be modified over time and a comprehensive monitoring plan is created to collect data on ecological, economic, and social indicators. The effectiveness of management actions is evaluated against the objectives using the collected data; then managers should use the evaluation results to improve future management actions and policy directions. The role of stakeholder engagement is crucial in shaping these objectives and evaluations, ensuring that the policy evolution is responsive to the needs and insights of all stakeholders, thereby fostering more effective and inclusive marine resource management.

6.3 Conflict Resolution

Disputes are common among stakeholders with different interests and values. Collaborative governance includes mechanisms for conflict resolution, ensuring that different perspectives are respected, and compromises are sought. Effective conflict resolution in the context of marine policies often depends on a combination of proactive and reactive strategies. Building trust, ensuring fair representation, and fostering transparency are essential components of a successful collaborative governance framework that can manage and resolve conflicts effectively.

- **Type of conflicts in marine policies:**
 - **Resources use conflicts:** disputes over-fishing rights, mineral extraction, shipping routes, and tourism activities.
 - **Environmental conservation vs. economic development:** tensions between protecting ecosystems and promoting industry or infrastructure projects.
- **Approaches to conflict resolution:**
 - **Mediation and negotiation:** a neutral third party can help facilitate discussions and mediate disputes to reach a mutually acceptable solution bringing together all affected parties to discuss their concerns and negotiate solutions.
 - **Consensus-building processes:** efforts to create agreements through inclusive, participatory processes that aim for consensus rather than majority rule.
 - **Arbitration:** in cases where negotiation fails, an arbitrator may make a binding decision based on the arguments presented by all sides.
- **Challenges in Conflict Resolution:**

- Power dynamics: conflicts can be exacerbated by power imbalances among stakeholders, where some may have more influence over outcomes than others.
- Differing values and interests: stakeholders may have fundamentally different values and priorities, making consensus difficult.
- Communication barriers: miscommunication or lack of communication can hinder the resolution of conflicts.
- Complex legal and regulatory frameworks: navigating the complexity of laws and regulations that govern marine spaces can be a source of conflict in itself.

6.3.1 Project examples

MERCES (Marine Ecosystem Restoration in Changing European Seas)

- Funded by: H2020
- **Objective:** This project aimed to restore degraded marine habitats across Europe to achieve good environmental status, focusing on the restoration of coralligenous and biogenic reefs and the recovery of populations of commercially important species.
- **Conflict Resolution Aspect:** MERCES engaged with stakeholders to address conflicts between conservation goals and economic activities like fishing and tourism, by restoring ecosystems that are vital both for biodiversity and for the economy.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689518>

AQUACROSS (Knowledge, Assessment, and Management for AQUatic Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services across EU policies)

- Funded by: H2020
- **Objective:** The AQUACROSS project sought to advance the application of ecosystem-based management for aquatic ecosystems to support the achievement of EU biodiversity targets.
- **Conflict Resolution Aspect:** It dealt with conflicts by developing management practices and guidance that integrate different policy objectives and the needs of various stakeholders across freshwater and marine environments.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/642317>

COMMON (COastal Management and MONitoring Network for tackling marine litter in Mediterranean sea) not in CORDIS, not in MOE database

- Funded by: EU, ENI CBCMED, Sardegna Region
- **Objective:** The COMMON project aims to improve coastal and marine environmental management and planning in the Mediterranean, with a focus on reducing marine litter.
- **Conflict Resolution Aspect:** The project involves cooperation among different Mediterranean countries and engages with local communities, NGOs, and governments to address the cross-border issue of marine litter.

COASTAL (Collaborative Land-Sea Integration Platform)

- Funded by: H2020
- **Objective:** COASTAL is a collaborative research project that creates business opportunities and improves the coastal-rural synergy to foster rural and coastal development while preserving the environment.

- **Conflict Resolution Aspect:** This project uses a multi-actor approach to resolve conflicts between land-based activities and marine conservation, encouraging sustainable economic development in coastal areas.
- CORDIS link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773782>

DiscardLess (Strategies for the gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries)

- Funded by: H2020
- **Objective:** The project's goal is to provide the knowledge, tools, and technologies as well as the involvement of the stakeholders to achieve the gradual elimination of discarding in European fisheries.
- **Conflict Resolution Aspect:** By involving stakeholders and considering the socio-economic impact of discarding policies, the project seeks to find balanced solutions to reduce discards without harming fishermen's livelihoods.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/633680>

CERES (Climate Change and European Aquatic RESources)

- Funded by: H2020
- **Objective:** CERES aims to provide a framework for evaluating the vulnerability of European marine and freshwater ecosystems and the services they provide to climate change.
- **Conflict Resolution Aspect:** The project involves stakeholder-driven scenarios to identify and resolve potential conflicts arising from climate change impacts on fisheries and aquaculture sectors.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** workshops, focus groups, interviews and correspondence
- CORDIS link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/678193>

6.4 Co-Management

Co-management represents a significant shift away from traditional management of marine resources. It recognizes that the people who use and depend on these resources—fishermen, coastal communities, indigenous groups, tourism operators, and conservationists—can be powerful allies in conservation and management efforts. By actively engaging these stakeholders directly in the decision-making process, co-management seeks to leverage their local knowledge, vested interest, and investment in the health of the ecosystems, leading to more effective and sustainable marine policies. Such engagement is essential, as it ensures that those most impacted by management decisions have a voice and are more likely to support and adhere to the agreed-upon regulations.

In the context of collaborative governance in marine policies, stakeholder engagement is a cornerstone of co-management—an arrangement where responsibility and authority for resource management are shared between the government and local resource users or communities. This approach is often contrasted with top-down governance, where decisions are made exclusively by centralized authorities without significant input from local stakeholders. In co-management schemes, decisions are made in a more decentralized manner, incorporating the knowledge and experience of those who are directly affected by the policies. Engaging stakeholders not only helps in reflecting diverse perspectives in policy-making but also builds trust, enhances policy acceptance, and fosters a shared sense of stewardship over marine resources.

- **Key Features:**

- Shared governance: co-management is characterized by shared power and responsibility between government entities and community groups or resource users.
- Participatory decision-making: local resource users are actively involved in the decision-making process, contributing local knowledge and vested interest in sustainable outcomes.
- Legal frameworks: effective co-management requires a supportive legal and institutional framework that legitimizes the co-management arrangement and clarifies the roles and responsibilities of all parties.
- Multi-level integration: co-management often functions best when it is integrated into broader governance frameworks, including regional, national, and even international policies and regulations.
- **Implementation**
 - Developing partnerships: building relationships and trust between government agencies and local stakeholders is foundational to co-management.
 - Negotiating agreements: co-management is usually formalized through agreements that define the scope, rights, and responsibilities of each party.
 - Capacity building: ensuring that all stakeholders, especially local communities, have the skills and resources needed to engage effectively in management activities.
 - Conflict resolution mechanisms: establishing processes for dealing with disputes is an important component of co-management agreements.
 - Monitoring and enforcement: in many co-management systems, local users play a significant role in monitoring resource use and enforcing regulations.
- **Benefits:**
 - Incorporates local expertise: local stakeholders often have a deep understanding of the ecosystem and can provide valuable insights.
 - Increases compliance: when local communities are involved in creating rules, there is generally a higher level of compliance with those rules.
 - Enhances resource stewardship: stakeholders who are involved in management are more likely to act as stewards of the resource, with a long-term view of sustainability.
 - Improves adaptive capacity: co-management systems can be more nimble and able to adapt to change because they can draw on a wide range of knowledge and experiences.

6.4.1 Project examples

BALANCE (Baltic Sea Management – Nature Conservation and Sustainable Development of the Ecosystem through Spatial Planning)

- **Funded by:** INTERREG III B Baltic Sea Region Programme
- **Objective:** To develop tools and approaches for marine spatial planning in the Baltic Sea.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** The project involved a wide range of marine stakeholders from different sectors to ensure that spatial planning reflects the needs and inputs of all users of the sea.
- **Link:** <https://balance-eu.org/>

COFASP (Cooperation in Fisheries, Aquaculture and Seafood Processing)

- **Funded by:** EU's 7th Framework Programme for research, technological development, and demonstration

- **Objective:** To lay the groundwork for cooperation in research and development to support the management of marine resources.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** It brought together various stakeholders from the fisheries, aquaculture, and seafood sectors to inform and guide research priorities.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/321553>

MareFrame (Co-creating Ecosystem-based Fisheries Management Solutions)

- **Funded by:** EU's 7th Framework Programme
- **Objective:** To improve fisheries management through the development of ecosystem-based solutions.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** The project emphasized co-creation with stakeholders, including fisheries professionals, policymakers, and scientists to develop tools and models for sustainable fisheries.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/613571>

MUSES (Multi-Use in European Seas)

- **Funded by:** Horizon 2020
- **Objective:** To explore multi-use potentials of marine resources, aiming to increase the compatibility of different uses of the sea.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** MUSES conducted a series of case studies across European seas and involved local stakeholders to understand the practicalities of multi-use concepts.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/727451>

SAFI (Sustainable Fisheries Agreements – Improved Monitoring and Evaluation)

- **Funded by:** European Development Fund
- **Objective:** To develop a framework for the monitoring and evaluation of sustainable fisheries agreements between the EU and non-EU countries.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** This project engaged with national and regional fisheries organizations, as well as local fishing communities, to ensure that sustainable fisheries agreements are effectively monitored and evaluated.
- **CORDIS link:** not in CORDIS, not link found

CleanAtlantic (Tackling Marine Litter in the Atlantic Area)

- **Funded by:** Interreg Atlantic Area Programme
- **Objective:** To protect biodiversity and ecosystem services in the Atlantic Area by improving the capability to monitor, prevent, and remove marine litter.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Involved stakeholders across the board, including NGOs, regional governments, the fishing industry, and scientific communities, to tackle the issue of marine litter collaboratively.
- **Link:** <http://www.cleanatlantic.eu/>

6.5 Policy Development and Implementation

Policy development and implementation is a complex, multi-stage process that involves various stakeholders, institutions, and interests. Collaborative governance recognizes the interdependent nature of marine ecosystems and the activities they support, necessitating a comprehensive and

inclusive approach to policy development. It seeks to create more resilient, adaptable, and inclusive policies that reflect the complex socio-ecological systems they aim to manage. Through active collaboration, policies are not only shaped by diverse perspectives but also gain broader acceptance and legitimacy, leading to more effective implementation and outcomes.

Stages:

1. Problem identification is the foundational step that determines the direction and focus of policy initiatives, where stakeholders and policymakers assess and prioritize issues based on their urgency, impact, and feasibility of intervention. It involves a thorough analysis of existing conditions, utilizing scientific data, stakeholder input, and socio-economic assessments to discern the root causes and potential scope of the policies needed to address them effectively.
2. Policy formulation is a critical stage where stakeholders synthesize information, goals, and constraints into viable policy options, drawing on evidence, expert opinions, and public input to craft strategic approaches. This process translates identified problems into structured policy proposals, articulating clear objectives, delineating implementation mechanisms, and setting the stage for decision-making and subsequent enactment.
3. Decision making is the juncture at which stakeholders evaluate and select from among the proposed policy options, balancing practicality, impact, and consensus to determine the most appropriate course of action. This phase is characterized by deliberation, negotiation, and ultimately, the authoritative determination of policies that will be adopted and moved forward into implementation, reflecting the collective judgment and commitment of the involved parties.
4. Policy implementation marks the transition from concept to action, where adopted policies are operationalized through the development of action plans, allocation of resources, and establishment of procedures and timelines. It involves the on-the-ground execution of policy decisions, necessitating coordination among various stakeholders and agencies to ensure that the objectives outlined in the policy are achieved effectively and efficiently.
5. Monitoring and evaluation are integral processes that provide ongoing feedback by systematically tracking the progress and outcomes of implemented policies against the set objectives and performance indicators. These critical functions not only measure effectiveness and inform adaptive management but also ensure accountability and support continuous improvement in policy interventions.
6. Enforcement and compliance are essential to ensuring that the established regulations and guidelines are adhered to, with clear mechanisms in place for monitoring adherence and applying sanctions when necessary. This stage reinforces the integrity of the policy framework by actively upholding standards, addressing violations, and fostering a culture of compliance through education and engagement with all stakeholders.
7. Review and adaptation involve the regular assessment of policy effectiveness and the incorporation of lessons learned to refine and improve policy measures, ensuring they remain relevant and responsive to changing circumstances. This iterative process allows policymakers to make informed adjustments that enhance policy outcomes, foster innovation, and sustain the policy's alignment with its overarching goals and the evolving needs of the community.

6.5.1 Project examples

Integrated Marine Policy Development and Implementation (IMP) not in CORDIS, not in MOE database

- **Funded by:** European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF)
- **Objective:** To support the development of an integrated policy that covers all aspects of the marine environment, from fisheries to environmental protection.
- **Details:** The project would typically involve analyzing current policies, engaging with stakeholders, and developing integrated management plans. The integrated approach is a hallmark of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), which is the EU's legal framework for the protection of the marine environment.

The COMMON Project (COastal Management and Monitoring Network for tackling marine litter in Mediterranean Sea) not in CORDIS, not in MOE database

- **Funded by:** ENI CBC Med Programme
- **Objective:** To promote a cross-border cooperation in the Mediterranean region for the management of marine litter.
- **Details:** This project involves multiple Mediterranean countries and focuses on sharing best practices, monitoring marine litter, and engaging local communities and stakeholders in policy-making processes.

MARINEPLAN (Marine Spatial Planning in the European Atlantic)

- **Funded by:** EMFF
- **Objective:** To develop cross-border marine spatial planning (MSP) to ensure that human activities at sea take place in an organized manner and under a common framework.
- **Details:** This project has included extensive stakeholder consultation to develop spatial plans that balance ecological, economic, and social objectives.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** co-development of a decision support system for MSP.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059407>

BENTHIS (Benthic Ecosystem Fisheries Impact Study)

- **Funded by:** EU's 7th Framework Programme
- **Objective:** To provide a better understanding of the impact of fisheries on benthic ecosystems, which is crucial for the development of ecosystem-based fisheries management.
- **Details:** The project's outcomes inform policy on the sustainable use of benthic resources, involving stakeholders in fisheries, environmental NGOs, and policy-makers.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** collaborate with industry and other stakeholders in testing the performance of innovative technologies to reduce fishing impact.
- **Link:** <http://www.benthis.eu/en/>

COLUMBUS (Monitoring, Managing and Transferring Marine and Maritime Knowledge for Sustainable Blue Growth)

- **Funded by:** Horizon 2020
- **Objective:** To ensure that outputs from EU-funded marine and maritime research are effectively transferred into innovation and policy.
- **Details:** It focused on knowledge transfer and provided recommendations for marine policy development based on the latest research findings.

- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/652690>

PERICLES (Preserving and Sustainably Governing Cultural Heritage and Landscapes in European Coastal and Maritime Regions)

- **Funded by:** Horizon 2020
- **Objective:** To develop sustainable management strategies and policies for cultural heritage in European coastal and maritime regions.
- **Details:** This project engaged with local and regional stakeholders to incorporate cultural heritage into marine spatial planning and policy-making.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/770504>

OceanGov (Global Ocean Governance: An International Regime Complex)

- **Funded by:** European Research Council (ERC)
- **Objective:** To analyze and improve the regime complex for the governance of the global oceans.
- **Details:** The project looks at how different marine policies at the international level interconnect and how they can be streamlined and implemented effectively.
- **CORDIS link:** not in CORDIS

6.6 Capacity Building and Education

Capacity building and education in the context of collaborative governance are about enabling all participants to contribute effectively to the management of marine resources. They involve not only transferring knowledge and skills but also fostering a collaborative culture and empowering stakeholders to take ownership of marine conservation and sustainable use efforts. This ensures that all parties have the knowledge and skills necessary to participate effectively in management and decision-making processes. The complex nature of marine governance, encompassing ecological, social, economic, and political dimensions, requires stakeholders to have a certain level of knowledge and skill to participate effectively.

- **Capacity Building** entails enhancing the ability of all stakeholders, including fishers, local communities, policymakers, and conservation groups, to engage meaningfully in the management of marine resources. By providing training, sharing knowledge, and developing leadership within these groups, stakeholders become more effective partners in governance, capable of contributing to the development, implementation, and monitoring of policies that impact marine ecosystems. This empowerment is crucial in addressing the complex challenges of marine conservation, ensuring that decision-making is informed, inclusive, and reflective of the multifaceted interests and expertise of those who depend on and care for marine environments. Through capacity building, stakeholders not only gain a deeper understanding of the ecological dynamics but also the socio-economic implications of marine policies, enabling a more resilient and adaptive approach to managing the oceans' vital resources.
- **Education** serves as a cornerstone, essential for cultivating a well-informed stakeholder base that can actively contribute to the sustainable management of marine ecosystems. Initiatives such as targeted training programs, educational workshops, and inclusive dialogue forums play a crucial role in disseminating knowledge on marine biodiversity, legal frameworks, and the socio-economic dimensions of marine conservation. Such educational efforts are designed not only to enhance the understanding of individual stakeholders but also to foster a collective sense of

stewardship and shared responsibility. By integrating traditional knowledge with scientific research, education can bridge gaps between different community sectors, ensuring that all voices are equipped to engage in the policy process. This informed engagement is critical for the formulation of marine policies that are not only ecologically sound but also socially equitable and economically viable, reflecting the collaborative spirit necessary for the long-term health and productivity of marine environments.

Challenges:

- a) Funding: securing long-term funding for capacity building and education programs can be a significant challenge.
- b) Cultural barriers: programs must be sensitive to and inclusive of local cultural norms and practices.
- c) Language and literacy: adapting materials to local languages and literacy levels is crucial for effective communication and learning.
- d) Retention of skills: ensuring that once trained, individuals remain in the community to apply their skills and knowledge can be difficult, particularly in regions with high levels of outmigration.
- e) Monitoring and evaluation: it's necessary to have mechanisms in place to assess the effectiveness of capacity building and education initiatives and make necessary adjustments.

Successful strategies:

- a) Local knowledge integration: recognizing and incorporating traditional ecological knowledge (TEK) with scientific knowledge in resource management.
- b) Participatory approaches: engaging stakeholders in the design and implementation of training programs to ensure they are relevant and meet their needs.
- c) Adaptive learning: establishing continuous learning processes that can adapt to changing environmental conditions and policy landscapes.
- d) Leveraging technology: using technology, such as online platforms, to extend the reach and accessibility of educational resources.

6.6.1 Project examples

MARES (Marine Ecosystems Health and Conservation)

- **Funded by:** Erasmus Mundus Programme
- **Objective:** To establish an international Master's program focused on marine ecosystem health and conservation, aimed at building the capacity of future scientists, policymakers, and managers.
- **Details:** The project connects universities, research institutions, and marine stakeholders to create a curriculum that combines academic knowledge with practical skills in marine conservation and management.
- **Not in CORDIS, not in MOE database**

MARINA (Marine Knowledge Sharing Platform for Federating Responsible Research and Innovation Communities)

- **Funded by:** Horizon 2020

- **Objective:** To develop and strengthen a platform for sharing knowledge and experiences on marine research and innovation, with a particular focus on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).
- **Details:** This project involves workshops, conferences, and online platforms to engage stakeholders and the public in marine issues and to foster a community of practice that supports sustainable marine governance.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/710566>

AquaVitae (New Species, Processes and Products Contributing to Increased Production and Improved Sustainability in Emerging Low Trophic, and Recirculating Aquaculture Value Chains)

- **Funded by:** Horizon 2020
- **Objective:** To enhance aquaculture production by introducing new species, improving processes, and developing innovative products.
- **Details:** The project involves capacity-building activities, including training modules and workshops for stakeholders in the aquaculture sector to ensure the sustainable expansion of this industry.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818173>

FishMPABlue2 (Fisheries Governance in Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas) not in CORDIS

- **Funded by:** Interreg MED Programme
- **Objective:** To enhance the governance of small-scale fisheries within and around Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in the Mediterranean.
- **Details:** The project offers training sessions, guidelines, and governance tools to local fishers, MPA managers, and other stakeholders to improve the sustainability of fisheries and the effectiveness of MPAs.

SEAwise (Sustainable, Profitable, and Resilient Small-Scale Fisheries Including a Climate Perspective)

- **Funded by:** Horizon Europe
- **Objective:** To enhance the sustainability and climate resilience of small-scale fisheries in European seas through co-creation and shared knowledge.
- **Details:** Stakeholder engagement and capacity building are key components, with training workshops, decision-support tools, and co-management strategies being developed in collaboration with fishers and other marine actors.
- **CORDIS link:** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000318>

EduMAR (Education for Sustainable Marine Governance) not in CORDIS

- **Funded by:** Erasmus+
- **Objective:** To foster education and training in marine governance, emphasizing sustainability and stakeholder engagement.
- **Details:** The project focuses on developing educational materials and courses that integrate scientific, regulatory, and practical aspects of marine governance for various stakeholders, including students, professionals, and policymakers.

BlueEDU (European Aquaculture Skills and Competencies) not in CORDIS

- **Funded by:** Erasmus+
- **Objective:** To identify skills gaps in the European aquaculture workforce and develop an educational framework to address these needs.

- **Details:** It involves collaboration with industry representatives, educational institutions, and policymakers to ensure that the aquaculture sector has a skilled workforce capable of supporting sustainable growth and collaborative governance.

Made with Whimsical

Figure 3. Effective collaborative management outcomes

7 Sustainability of Stakeholder engagement and communication

Ensuring the sustainability of stakeholder engagement in your project is crucial for building and maintaining positive relationships with stakeholders over the long term. Effective communication plays a central role in achieving this sustainability.

Maintain clear and transparent communication channels with stakeholders. Ensure that information is readily available and easy to understand. Be open about project goals, progress, challenges, and decisions. Foster two-way communication with stakeholders. Encourage them to voice their opinions, concerns, and ideas. Create multiple feedback mechanisms, such as surveys, public forums, and feedback portals. Provide regular project updates to keep stakeholders informed about developments, milestones, and changes. Establish a communication schedule and adhere to it. Tailor your communication to different stakeholder groups. Understand their unique needs, preferences, and concerns. Use appropriate language and channels to engage effectively. Utilize a variety of communication platforms to reach different kinds of stakeholders. These may include social media, websites, newsletters, email updates, meetings, webinars, and public consultations. Be prepared to address conflicts and disagreements through effective communication. Establish a conflict resolution process that is fair, impartial, and respectful of stakeholder perspectives. Periodically review your engagement and communication strategies. Be willing to adjust and refine your approach based on feedback, lessons learned, and changing stakeholder dynamics.

8 Monitoring and evaluation of stakeholder engagement

It is clear that monitoring and evaluating the project objectives themselves, assess them and share insights with your stakeholders is the first step. If you wish to also measure the effectiveness of the stakeholder engagement in your specific project, you might define specific objectives for the stakeholder engagement processes in your specific project. These objectives should be measurable and aligned with the project's overall goals, and differ per kind of stakeholder (which you have identified in an earlier stage). It can help to work with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): relevant parameters that will help you measure the effectiveness of stakeholder engagement. KPIs might include the number of stakeholder meetings, the level of satisfaction, the frequency of feedback, and the resolution of stakeholder issues, but encompass all relevant factors defined by the project manager. Create formal and informal feedback channels for stakeholders to express their opinions, concerns, and suggestions. These mechanisms can include surveys, focus groups, interviews, suggestion boxes, or dedicated email addresses. The mechanisms frequency will depend of the project resources, best is to document the feedback. Key is to always stay attuned to evolving stakeholder expectations and concerns. Be flexible and ready to adjust your engagement strategies as stakeholder needs change. Monitor the progress and status of resolving issues or addressing concerns raised by stakeholders, these are your means in the field. Determine if stakeholders are receiving the right information at the right time. Create regular reports or dashboards that provide an overview of stakeholder engagement performance. Additionally, it is important to share the results of your monitoring efforts with stakeholders. Use the feedback received from stakeholders to fine-tune engagement strategies and go from monitoring towards informing as well on project decisions and actions. Periodically, seek external reviews or audits of your stakeholder engagement process to gain an independent perspective on its effectiveness.

Benefits of monitoring and evaluating the conflicts in engagement projects: better planning of SHE, focus on the objectives, measure success and how to do bring more values and benefits, help informing, changing, improving, demonstrate value of money, show SH their contribution's impact. Monitor success, process and impact is key.

Further explanation on stakeholder engagement monitoring in environmental projects can be found in The Biodiversa Stakeholder Engagement Handbook¹⁵ which is a non-academic practical guide for researchers planning and carrying out research projects.

¹⁵ Stakeholder Engagement Handbook – Biodiversa +. Open Source Handbook: <https://www.biodiversa.eu/library/#1>

9 Choose the right engagement model for the Mission based on data available: online tool

Taking into account all the above considerations for conducting stakeholder engagement, PREP4BLUE have developed an online tool that can help choose the right model of engagement for projects that contribute to the Mission Ocean and waters objectives. We would like here to give a quick overview of how the online tool looks like and what are the main functionalities of the tool. The online tool is part of the Wavelinks web platform jointly developed under the CSA projects PREP4BLUE, BlueMissionBANOS and BlueMissionAA and can be found at the following address: www.wavelinks.eu. In annex we are giving more details on how data on stakeholder engagement methods was collected to build the tool.

The landing page of the tool is a page where the users can browse or search through the list of methods for stakeholder engagement. A screenshot of the landing page of the tool in its v0.3 version is presented below (Figure 4). The initial list of method has been collected by identifying EU projects linked to the Mission Ocean that mentions stakeholder engagement in their project description. This initial list will be enriched over time by users of the tool who will be able to input new methods and use cases in the database.

Name	Targeted Groups	Level Of Engagement	Purpose Of Engagement	Participants	Duration	Data Source
> Newsletter	Media	Inform	Provide the public with balanced and objec...	Any	Ongoing	item
> Printed media appearances	Media	Inform	Distribute flyers, banners, and posters to pr...	Any	1-7 days	item
> Project website	Government Academia	Inform	Present detailed descriptions of project goals...	Any	Ongoing	item
> Open Innovation - crowdsourcing	Academia Civil Society Government...	Consult	Harvest collective intelligence and creativit...	10-1000	1-50 days	item
> Social media	Government Media Industry...	Inform	Distribute small updates and facts about th...	Any	Ongoing	item
> Newsletter	Media	Inform	Provide the public with balanced and objec...	Any	Ongoing	item
> Printed media appearances	Media	Inform	Distribute flyers, banners, and posters to pr...	Any	1-7 days	item

Figure 4. Screenshot of the landing page of the online tool v0.3.

To search through the list of methods, users can use three different ways:

- Filtering the list according to different variables: level of engagement, number of stakeholders to be engaged, targeted stakeholder groups, duration of the engagement, countries/regions where the methods have been used in the past, etc.;
- Writing in the search bar the name of a stakeholder engagement method;
- Writing in the search bar a keyword or short text that describe the topic of the project in which they want to engage stakeholders.

We envision two groups of users for the tool:

- The first group of users will already know a method they want to use to engage stakeholders in their project, and would like to get more information on how it was used in previous EU projects;
- The second group of users is looking for a relevant method of engagement to use in the context of their project. They might know which groups of stakeholders they want to engage and at which level of engagement for example, but they do not know which method they can use.

The first group of users, interested in getting more information on how a method of engagement has been used in the past in EU projects linked to the Mission Ocean is able to use the search bar and enter the name of the method to search through the list. Once the user found the method of interest in the list, they can open the detail page of the method by clicking on its name and they can see a more detailed description of the method as shown in the screenshot below (Figure 5). On the detail page, the user can also see in which context and projects the method of interest has been used in the past. The tool displays the acronym of projects that have used the method (as described in their deliverables) and presents visualizations of the topics covered by these projects, the countries of the participants in these projects etc... A screenshot of the prototype detail page of the method “Dilemmas café” is shown below as an example (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Prototype detail page for the method "Dilemmas cafe"

Users looking for relevant method(s) to use in the context of their Mission Ocean project can use the search bar and/or filters to look through the list of methods. They can use the filters on top of the list

of methods if they already know for example in which country they want to involve stakeholders or the level of engagement of the stakeholders they would like to achieve. Multiple categories can be selected for each filter and once selected, the number of results will be limited to the methods that correspond to the categories selected. On the screenshot below (Figure 6), we can see the selection of the level of engagement “inform” by a user. The list of methods is then restricted to methods that can be used to inform stakeholders.

Figure 6. Screenshot of the v0.3 of the tool that illustrate the selection of filters by the users.

Users searching for a method of engagement without much pre-conceived ideas in mind, they can enter in the search bar:

- Keywords describing their project or purpose/topic of engagement;
- Free text describing the topic of their project.

When using this type of search, the algorithm of the tool looks for projects matching these keywords or free text in the list of EU projects, linked to the Mission, and that have used engagement methods (as described in their deliverables), and subsequently return to the user the methods that have been used in these similar EU projects. The method at the top of the list is the one most used in the similar projects. The list of methods used in similar projects can be refined by using the filters as described above.

The entire list of methods and/or the methods returned as the result of a user search can be exported at any time by the user as CSV file using the “CSV” button at the bottom of the list of methods.

The tool is a living tool that evolves and will get enriched along the Mission’s progress and development. For that purpose, users are able to input new stakeholder engagement methods in the database. Users can link these new methods to projects they already know have used them. These new methods will also be automatically matched to the deliverables of all projects of the database to establish more links and enrich users’ data. Input of users will be reviewed by experts before being published online. Below we show a screenshot of the page that will allow users to input new methods in the database (tool v0.3).

10 Conclusion

This deliverable examines the optimal approach to identify, map, and engage stakeholders aligned with the objectives outlined in the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters." The proposed strategy aims to facilitate the achievement of a sustainable blue economy and the specified targets and objectives in alignment with the Mission. These guidelines are universally applicable across all four focal points: the Atlantic and Arctic Ocean, the Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic and North Sea, and the Danube River and Black Sea. They serve as an important baseline for the different LHs.

It is crucial to note that, given the presence of limited budgets for most if not all projects, stakeholder engagement is context-dependent. Therefore, it is recommended to tailor the identification of the most relevant actors, possessing significant and legitimate influence, as well as efficient management and budget allocation, to the specific context of each action or project. Current guidelines explain in detail how this can be done.

PREP4BLUE conducted an analysis of the work plans for 2021-2022 and 2022-2023 to identify key stakeholders to be engaged by lighthouses based on their specific objectives. The analysis conducted by P4B also considered the most effective methods to achieve certain goals of the Mission, including increasing awareness among stakeholders about the Mission's objectives, programs, tools, and their potential contributions.

Additionally, the report emphasizes the importance of enacting legislation that formally codifies the legal framework to align with existing laws. Granting stakeholders a legal right to participate in the stakeholder process in a legitimate manner is expected to be invaluable in the years to come, an important finding of the team of experts consulted, amongst others during the workshop.

Lastly, the team developed a database featuring various relevant projects within the Mission. These projects underwent identification and assessment of stakeholder engagement activities. The criteria used in selecting projects and methodologies aim to guide future project managers and society in choosing the most effective methods for stakeholder engagement. This contributes to the success of projects and fosters interest among stakeholders directly involved as partners in Mission-supported or funded projects, actions submitted to the Mission charter, and stakeholders engaged or to be engaged by such projects or actions.

11 Annexes

11.1 Rationale and program workshop Stakeholders2cO-design

“PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters”

stakeholders2cO-design ! Towards impactful stakeholder engagement in the Mission Ocean, Seas and Waters

Aiming to co-create and co-implement the research and innovation required to achieve the targets set by the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 (MO)”, Blue Cluster and CPMR co-organise a workshop on stakeholder engagement on 17 October 2023 in Brussels. As a part of the Horizon Europe Prep4Blue project, the team maps and assesses multidisciplinary, multi-stakeholder strategies involving industry, public authorities, citizens, academia and associations while envisaging the natural environment as key for social innovation and to efficiently bring society closer to the ocean. Lighthouse based challenges such as and not limited to carbon neutrality, circularity, biodiversity enhancement as well as reducing pollution are discussed.

Additionally, the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process that aims to identify areas for investment in R&I through an inclusive and evidence-based process, involving all stakeholders from the quadruple helix model to reach the MO goals is highlighted. This process is used for the elaboration and implementation of regional S3, the regional strategy for investments in R&I. Through the Partnerships for Regional Innovation, the JRC reflected on the concept of an Open Discovery Process to maximise stakeholder engagement and co-creation and develop challenge- or mission-oriented innovation policies.

As this workshop takes place under the umbrella of the EU week of regions and cities, this session presents this new approach, with concrete examples of the EDP from the regions, and interregional stakeholder linkages. We wish to showcase best practices to be included in the PREP4BLUE tool, discuss potential challenges and issues and identify how the project and the MO can support stakeholder engagement in the development and implementation of innovation policies in EU maritime regions. Ideally we further enrich the communities and interlink and map the stakeholder ecosystem related to the MO.

A digital toolbox assessing criteria dependent methodologies along with its guidelines as well as policy advice towards the needs and challenges of future missions are being drafted and shall be tested. The aim of this workshop is to finetune stakeholder engagement methodologies and their accuracy for the MO while gathering valuable input of key experts, as well as to put all participants in contact with their relevant European network. Welcome!

Locations

Day Troonstraat 100, 1050 Elsene

Night Talk CEC. Waversesteenweg 143, 1050 Elsene

AGENDA

- 09:00 Registration and coffee
- 09:15 Introduction on MO, Prep4Blue and today (Marijn Rabaut, senior MSP expert Blue Cluster)

A. The challenge of Stakeholder engagement in the Mission Oceans

- 09:45 How to bring society closer to the ocean and biodiversity. Pitfalls and opportunities of methodology selection (Matthew Smith, Co-Author BiodivERsA)
- 10:10 Co-creative design of large-scale projects. Infrastructures in marine environment: stakeholder involvement and carbon neutrality (Timothy Vanagt, senior project manager ORG)
- 10:35 Marine pollution prevention and mitigation, focus on stakeholder engagement (Marisa Fernandez, coordinator department 'control/management of marine environment and resources' CETMAR)
- 11:00 Coffee!
- 11:10 Panel discussion with key speakers and experts (you)

B. Stakeholder engagement in R&I regional policy: Open Discovery Process – Smart Specialisation Strategies

- 13:00 Presentation of the concept/theoretical approach (JRC Expert and/or EC representative) (tbc)
- 13:20 Partnerships for Regional Innovation – Feedback Azores region, as co-leader of the Working Group on the Open Discovery Process and local missions (CHOIRs) (Francisco Pinto, Senior Public Officer, Azores S3 Support Unit, Regional Directorate of Science and Technology) tbc)
- 13:40 Best practice of stakeholder engagement in the elaboration of mission-oriented policies – Shared agendas in Catalonia, Tatiana Fernandez, Head of Unit Economic Strategy, Catalan Government (tbc)
- 14:00 Interactive session
- 14:50 Coffee!

C. Tool DEMO and input

- 15:00 Stakeholder engagement methodology assessment (Maéva Vignes, project manager SDU)
- 15:30 Interactive session to fine-tune tool
- 16:50 Wrap-up and conclusions of the day

D. Networking

- 18:00 Cocktail + walking dinner – Immersive experience on seas and oceans @Talk CEC
- 22:00 It's Closing Time

11.2 Milestone 18 – concept note outlining a stakeholder engagement strategy for the Mission Oceans, Seas and Water

This document outlines a summary of the strategy for Stakeholder involvement (SHES) with significant findings based on the Workshop “*Stakeholders2cO-design! Towards impactful SHENG in the Mission Oceans, Seas and Water*”. **It forms the connection between D6.1 and D6.2 and marks an important Milestone within WP6.**

The underlying vision inspiring the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (SHES) is based on the principles of dynamism, inclusivity, and sustainability. The vision recognizes the vital importance of involving a diverse range of stakeholders in the Mission. Central to this vision is the concept of active and regular engagement through dialogues, collaborative governance, and adaptive management. The goal is to not just hear but actively address the varied interests and needs of stakeholders. This approach emphasizes creating continuous communication channels such as forums and data-sharing platforms that align with national and regional priorities, allowing for real-time feedback. Key pillars in maintaining positive, long-term relationships include transparency, effective communication, and conflict resolution.

Therefore, the SHES extends beyond mere engagement to encompass training, workshops, recognition, and collaborative projects, especially in the private sector, fostering sustainable practices.

At its core, the SHES commits to environmental sustainability, economic prosperity, and community involvement, creating a cohesive society benefiting optimally from ecosystem services, energy, and food supply.

This vision integrates participatory governance, ensuring that citizens and stakeholders are co-creators during the whole process.

In line with this vision, the introduction of the Mission Lighthouses as local business and citizen engagement hubs, along with a digital ocean and water knowledge system, reflects a forward-thinking approach. These initiatives not only enhance the understanding and forecasting of ecosystem health but also promote broad societal engagement. The Mission Implementation Platform (MIP Ocean) will play a crucial role in realizing the vision, serving as a central hub for mission monitoring, progress tracking, and integrating actions, facilitating collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders.

This dynamic vision will evolve with the progress of the Mission, remaining open to incorporating new stakeholder engagement methods. Its alignment with international governance standards and a focus on digital engagement ensures relevance to current challenges and responsiveness to emerging global trends and stakeholder needs.

Addressing the challenge of incorporating a wide variety of stakeholders into the increasing complexity of blue developments in a sustainable way is crucial. Within the objectives of the Mission, this involves tackling pollution, increasing biodiversity, reducing the carbon footprint, and accelerating circular processes in offshore business and other innovative activities at sea. Involving stakeholders is key to raising awareness, achieving project targets, managing risks, sharing best practices, reducing conflicts transparently, accessing resources and information, and identifying gaps accurately.

The overall strategy is rooted in the Penta-Helix model. A non-exhaustive stakeholder map presented in this deliverable D6.1, providing examples per country, serves as the basis.

The Stakeholder Engagement Strategy seeks to empower stakeholders through deliberative democracy, social innovation, and citizen science, activating their role in driving transitions and ensuring that no community is left.

11.3 List of methods for tool development

The initial list of method collected for the SHEM online tool can be seen below (Table 14) with their corresponding level of engagement.

Table 14. Initial list of methods collected for the SHEM online tool

Method	Level of engagement
Newsletter	Inform
Project website	Inform
Social media	Inform
Printed media (appearances)	Inform
Storymap (infographic website)	Inform
Media appearances (audio/video)	Inform
High-level outreach	Inform
Conferences and events	Inform/consult
Stakeholder meetings	Inform/consult
Virtual communities	Inform/consult
Real life communities or networks	Inform/consult
Open meetings/Town hall meetings	Inform/consult
Public consultation	Inform/consult
Exposition/work ateliers	Inform/consult
Survey	Consult
User group	Consult
DELPHI (meta method for questionnaires)	Consult
Regnier's Abacus (meta method for workshops)	Consult
Joint focus workshops	Consult/involve
Focus groups	Consult/involve
Semi structured interviews	Consult/involve
Role play: Actor constellation	Consult/involve
Dilemmas cafe	Consult/involve
Case studies and working groups	Consult/involve
World café	Consult/involve
Ecosystem Service assessment (ESA)	Consult/involve
Deliberative Mapping/Mind mapping	Involve
Online Discussions	Involve
Civic monitoring	Involve
Open Innovation - crowdsourcing	Involve
Start-up action: business plan competition	Involve
Summer/winter school	Involve/empower
Citizen Science	Involve/empower
Capacity Building	Involve/empower
Gamification	Involve/empower

Hackaton	Involve/empower
Foresight/future scenario workshops	Involve/empower
Co-creation sessions/workshops	Involve/empower
Research agenda camp – co-creation workshops	Involve/empower
Participatory Planning	Involve/empower
Webinar/web-based training	Empower
Business match-making events	Empower
Think tank	Empower
Living Labs	Empower
Action research	Empower
Participatory budgeting	Empower
Open Space Technology	Empower

All the method in the list above have been used in EU projects related to Mission objectives (later referred to as SHEM list. To obtain this list we combined qualitative and quantitative approaches. We first identified EU projects, from the CORDIS database, that described the used of stakeholder engagement methods in their project description by using RegEx¹⁶ searches. Using RegEx searches allowed us to find projects that in their summaries mentions any variation and conjugations of the words “stakeholder”, “engagement”, “consultation” and “inclusion”. This resulted in a list of 3783 projects, which were further narrowed down to 650 projects, using Latent Dirichlet Allocation (a topic modelling algorithm), to only include projects related to Mission objectives. Apart from the topic modelling, the European Science Vocabulary¹⁷ was also used for a series of RegEx searches, to overcome shortcomings of the topic modelling approach. This resulted in an additional 166 projects. Finally, when the EC Portfolio¹⁸ and Dashboard¹⁹ of projects linked to the Mission was published, we also searched through these projects (if they were not already included in our mapping) for the ones that mentioned stakeholder engagement methods in their project description.

From here a more manual qualitative process was initiated, reading through a sample of 161 deliverables on stakeholder engagement and communication and dissemination from 65 distinct projects. This was done in part to identify stakeholder engagement methods for the SHEM list, as well as to see if there were a certain pattern in these deliverables, that can be exploited for automatizing this process.

Besides scraping CORDIS for projects an effort has been made to identify Blue Balance projects that applies SHEM and integrate these methods and projects into the SHEM list.

After consolidating the initial list of SHEM by consulting stakeholder engagement experts in PREP4BLUE, we automatically established links between the methods identified to the projects

¹⁶ Regular Expression https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Regular_expression

¹⁷ European Science Vocabulary (EuroSciVoc) : <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/euroscivoc>

¹⁸ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/dfc5df4f-0073-11ee-87ec-01aa75ed71a1>

¹⁹ https://dashboard.tech.ec.europa.eu/qs_digit_dashboard_mt/public/sense/app/630dc6b8-23f3-43a1-a275-7a59115f3813/overview

included in our database as linked to the Mission Ocean that mentioned the use of any of these methods in their deliverables.

11.4 Interlinkages between projects and SHEMA

These efforts have resulted in the list of stakeholder engagement methods above, which can be viewed in more details and are linked to specific projects in the SHEMA list. We expect that linking methods to projects can both help exemplify how methods are used and help users of the tool find methods that fit their projects. This can also help in identifying methods that are used in conjunction with each other, as certain clusters of projects might use a similar combination of methods. Below in Figure 7, we have illustrated how several methods of engagement can be linked through the projects in which they were used (and vice-versa).

Figure 7. Example network of 3 projects using 4 engagement methods.